

D4.5 WILSON KPIs life-cycle oriented indicators panel

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The Deliverable presents a panel of KPIs to monitor and evaluate the developed solutions' results and level of innovation. The KPIs proposed will also make it possible to evaluate the performance of the demonstration sites and indicate, where necessary, the sensors to be installed for a proper monitoring plan during and after the WILSON project. This activity is part of Work Package 4 (WP4).	

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TABLE OF CONTENTS

1.	EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	7
2.	INTRODUCTION	8
2.1.	Scope of the deliverable	8
2.2.	Structure of the deliverable	8
2.3.	Relation with other tasks and deliverables.....	9
3.	METHODOLOGICAL APPROACH	10
3.1.	Summary of the main assumptions in the deliverable	13
4.	BUILDING LIFE CYCLE PHASES AND LINKS WITH WILSON “SUITE OF SOLUTIONS”	14
4.1.	Building Life Cycle Phases.....	14
4.2.	WILSON Suite of Solutions	15
4.2.1.	INN1 – 3: Data and Interoperability Toolset	16
4.2.2.	INN4 – 5: Planning and Management Toolset	21
4.2.3.	INN6 – 7: Environmental performance Toolset.....	25
4.2.4.	INN8 – 9: Building Diagnostics Toolset.....	29
4.2.5.	KER10: Investment Planning Tool	34
5.	LIFE CYCLE ORIENTED INDICATORS PANEL (PANEL OF KPIS)	36
5.1.	Panel of KPIs.....	38
5.1.1.	General and Pilot Common KPIs	38
5.1.2.	Data and Interoperability Indicators	39
5.1.3.	Planning and Management Indicators.....	42
5.1.4.	Environmental Performance Indicators	49
5.1.5.	Building Diagnostic Indicators.....	50
5.1.6.	Techno-economic Indicators	53
5.2.	Contingency KPIs	54
6.	HIGH-PRIORITY KPIS FOR BASELINE ASSESSMENT AND MONITORING PLAN	55
6.1.	Italian Demosite: Ex-Caserma Papa.....	55
6.2.	Spanish Demosite: Hospital del Mar	56
6.3.	UK Demosite: Newcastle HELIX	57
6.4.	Swiss Demosite: Building Park Uzwil	58
7.	CONCLUSIONS	60
8.	REFERENCES.....	62

LIST OF FIGURES

Figure 3.1: Multi-stage methodology approach	11
Figure 3.2: S.M.A.R.T. Framework.....	12
Figure 4.1: System diagram illustrating the processes that are included in the product system, divided into life-cycle stages and information modules (EPD International AB).....	15

LIST OF TABLES

Table 4.1: INN1 – General Information	16
Table 4.2: INN1 – Building Life Cycle Phases	16
Table 4.3: INN2 – General Information.....	17
Table 4.4: INN2 – Building Life Cycle Phases.....	18
Table 4.5: INN3 – General Information	19
Table 4.6: INN3 – Building Life Cycle Phases.....	20
Table 4.7: INN4 – General Information	21
Table 4.8: INN4 – Building Life Cycle Phases.....	22
Table 4.9: INN5 – General Information	23
Table 4.10: INN5 – Building Life Cycle Phases	24
Table 4.11: INN6 – General Information	25
Table 4.12: INN6 – Building Life Cycle Phases	26
Table 4.13: INN7 – General Information	27
Table 4.14: INN7 – Building Life Cycle Phases.....	28
Table 4.15: INN8 – General Information.....	29
Table 4.16: INN8 – Building Life Cycle Phases	30
Table 4.17: INN9 – General Information.....	31
Table 4.18: INN9 – Building Life Cycle Phases	33
Table 4.19: KER10 – General Information.....	34
Table 4.20: KER10 – Building Life Cycle Phases.....	35
Table 4.21: Mapping of the correlation between Building Phases and Tools.....	35
Table 5.1: General and Pilot Common KPIs.....	38
Table 5.2: Data and Interoperability Indicators.....	39
Table 5.3: Planning and Management Indicators.....	42
Table 5.4: Environmental Performance Indicators	49
Table 5.5: Building Diagnostic Indicators.....	51
Table 5.6: Techno-economic Indicators	53
Table 6.1: High-Priority/Baseline KPIs for Italian Pilot.....	56
Table 6.2: High-Priority/Baseline KPIs for Spanish Pilot	57
Table 6.3: High-Priority/Baseline KPIs for UK Pilot.....	58
Table 6.4: High-Priority/Baseline KPIs for Swiss Pilot	59

LIST OF ACRONYMS

ADD	Agenzia del Demanio
API	Application Programming Interface
BAFh	Harmonized Biotype Area Factor
BIM	Building Information Modelling
BMS	Building Management Systems
CAIDI	Customer Average Interruption Duration Index
CAIFI	Customer Average Interruption Frequency Index
CCI	Cooling Comfort Index
CP	Charging Points
CTAIDI	Customer Total Average Interruption Duration Index
EE	Electric Energy
ESC-B	Electricity self-consumption at Building Level
ESS-B	Electricity self-sufficiency at Building Level
EV	Electric Vehicles
FWEP	Freshwater Eutrophication
GIS	Geographic Information System
GWFE	Global Warning for Freshwater Ecosystem
GWP	Global Warming Potential
GWTE	Global Warning for Terrestrial Ecosystem
HCI	Heating Comfort Index
HVAC	Heating, Cooling & Air Conditioning
IFC	Industry Foundation Classes
INN	Innovation
IoT	Internet of Things
KF	Key-Functionalities
KPI	Key Performance Indicators
LCA	Life-cycle assessment
N/A	Not Applicable
P2P	Peer2Peer
PCR	Product Category Rules
PDH	Personalised Building Data Hubs
RES	Renewable Energy Sources
RUL	Remaining Useful Life
SAIDI	System Average Interruption Duration Index Reduction
SAIFI	System Average Interruption Frequency Index
SRES-B	Share of Renewable at Building Level
SRI	Smart Readiness Indicator
TA	Terrestrial Acidification
UCs	Use Cases
WCAE	Water consumption for aquatic ecosystems
WCTE	Water consumption for Terrestrial ecosystem

1. EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This report presents the work conducted in Task 4.5 of the WILSON project. The objective is to develop a panel of KPIs to monitor and evaluate the results and level of innovation of the developed solutions. The sources of information for the elaboration of these KPIs are derived from the analysis of the potential impacts in terms of data management, operation, sustainability, and resilience. These KPIs will also make it possible to evaluate the performance of the demonstration sites across a wide range of items and indicate, where necessary, the requirements and sensors to be installed for a proper monitoring plan during and after the WILSON project. This activity is part of Work Package 4 (WP4).

The identification of KPIs followed a multi-stage methodological approach, illustrated in Figure 3.1, which required input from all partners involved in the development of the Innovations. This stage was supported by data collection through dedicated questionnaires and bilateral meetings. The technical development of the KPIs was based on the S.M.A.R.T. framework, as shown in Figure 3.2. To support the analysis, a detailed study of the different phases of the building life cycle (design, production, construction, use and end of life) was conducted with the aim of identifying the specific benefits that each innovation can bring to each phase.

The KPIs, organised by innovation clusters, were first prioritised on a scale from 0 (low-priority) to 2 (high-priority), also due to the large number of potentially evaluable indicators, and then, for those classified as priority 2, linked to the different pilots in order to identify a first set of high-level indicators that could potentially be used for an initial baseline definition and monitoring plan. The remaining indicators of lower priority are reported to encourage discussion among project partners and to assess the specificities of the pilots and use cases in the next upcoming implementation and evaluation phase. From these, additional contingency KPIs may be identified.

To ensure a precautionary analysis and to maintain the objective of verifying the expected results of the project, certain operational assumptions have been made and the link between KPIs and Pilots has only been made for high-priority indicators. Once the implementation phase starts and the technologies are developed, it will be possible to link the lower priority KPIs to the individual pilots and use cases.

In conclusion, the proposed “Panel of KPIs” allow both to measure the level of innovation of the Innovations and to assess the performance of the buildings and the portfolio, but they can also help stakeholders in the decision-making phases to support the planned interventions, with particular attention to the entire life cycle of the asset.

Given the large number of indicators provided, it is recommended to regularly review their applicability during the demonstration phase of the project and to assess the possible inclusion of new indicators, if necessary.

2. INTRODUCTION

The built environment is facing increasingly complex challenges, including climate change, social inequality, and resource depletion. In this context, it is essential to develop new solutions that can guide, and support decision-making related to the built environment, addressing not only energy issues, which have already been extensively analysed and developed, but also environmental, social, and economic factors throughout the entire life cycle of a building.

To address these challenges, the WILSON Project proposes *“a ground-breaking approach leveraging semantic data repositories, cognitive digital twins, and decentralised data management to transform the management of buildings and building portfolios”* (WILSON Website). To this end, WILSON aims to develop *“holistic, extensible, and decentralised data mesh architecture addressing data management which will be agnostic to and interoperable with existing, proprietary BMS and Digital Twin Systems”* (WILSON Website).

This decentralized system will allow the integration of a *“Suite of Solutions”* focused on improving the overall building performance and supporting decision-making processes, through (European Commission, WILSON Partners, 2024):

1. Enhancing building operations through better planning and management;
2. Evaluating environmental impact and circularity;
3. Advanced and more precise building diagnostics and monitoring.

2.1. Scope of the deliverable

Considering the objectives promoted by the WILSON Project, Deliverable 4.5 will report a specific Panel of Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) able to assess the innovation and effectiveness of WILSON solutions, but also to evaluate the performance of the Pilots sites and indicate, where necessary, the sensors to be installed for a proper monitoring plan during and after the WILSON project. To achieve these results, contributions from all consortium partners were gathered in various forms, including data collections questionnaires and specific meetings.

2.2. Structure of the deliverable

Except for Chapter 1, which consists of the *“Executive Summary”* and Chapter 2, which provides the actual *“Introduction”*, the Deliverable is structured as follows:

- **Chapter 3** provides detailed information on the methodological approach adopted in Task 4.5 for the development of the KPI Panel and the main assumption;
- **Chapter 4** describes the different phases of a building life cycle and the set of solutions proposed within WILSON project. This chapter is crucial for understanding the relationship between the *“Suite of Solutions”* and the buildings;
- **Chapter 5** introduces the *“Panel of KPIs”*, providing the necessary context to understand its structure and purpose, along with the list of contingency KPIs;

- **Chapter 6** presents, for each Pilot, an initial set of KPIs that could be potentially assessed, given the current status of the projects and the information available. These KPIs could be used to define an “as-is” or baseline performance and initial monitoring plan of each pilot, building or asset against which future comparisons could be made and the effectiveness of the project assessed. These KPIs are of the highest priority.
- **Chapter 7** presents the main outcomes and the author’s conclusion, and;
- **Chapter 8** reports the references used for the elaboration of the document.

2.3. Relation with other tasks and deliverables

The Panel of KPIs, developed with the support of consortium partners, was designed to assess the innovation and effectiveness of the WILSON solutions, as well as to analyse the pilot performances, both energy and non-energy, according to the proposed INNOvations capacities.

The panel was initially developed by analysing the technical information collected through a questionnaire distributed to tool developers. Subsequently, to ensure alignment with the use and business cases, and to verify the pilot sites' interest, its development followed the activities described in deliverable D4.2, “WILSON Use and Business Cases Definition”. This parallel approach was essential for identifying and prioritising KPIs based on the pilots' interests and the use and business case objectives. Deliverable 4.2 is publicly available.

This KPI Panel will serve as a reference starting point for future project activities, including the development of pilot sites and the monitoring plan, which is expected by the end of 2026 and will be publicly available as deliverable D13.1 “Development and Monitoring Plan”. Furthermore, it will support the evaluation of results, impact assessment, and Cost-Benefit Analysis, which will be published at the end of the project (April 2028) in the public deliverable D15.1 “Evaluation of key results, impact assessment and CBA”.

All publicly available deliverables related to the WILSON Project are, or will be, accessible at the following links:

- WILSON Public Deliverable Library: <https://wilson-project.eu/public-deliverables/>;
- CORDIS - EU research results: <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101147267>.

3. METHODOLOGICAL APPROACH

To achieve the goal of creating a *"holistic, extensible, and decentralised data mesh architecture addressing data management which will be agnostic to and interoperable with existing, proprietary BMS and Digital Twin Systems"* (European Commission, WILSON Partners, 2024), WILSON proposes the development of 9 different innovations, referred to by the acronym INN. These INNs, designed and developed by WILSON engineers, aim to support decision-making processes in the built environment throughout the entire life cycle of a building or building portfolios.

These 9 INNs, which will be described in more detail in section 4.2, are grouped into 4 different clusters, each of them with specific objectives and targets:

- Cluster 1, called "Data and Interoperability";
- Cluster 2, called "Planning and Management";
- Cluster 3, called "Environmental performance"; and
- Cluster 4, called "Building Diagnostics".

In addition to the aforementioned innovations, a tenth innovation was also introduced into the current analysis, called the *"Planning Investment Tool"*, which enables the technical-economic characterisation of the proposed solutions and guides stakeholders in choosing the most advantageous innovative action. Performance indicators were also provided for this tool.

Therefore, once the boundaries and objectives of the analysis have been clearly introduced, the aim of this deliverable is to report and characterise a set of KPIs that allow to assess and monitor the impact and effectiveness of all the innovation proposed and the overall improvement of the building's performance in its entirety and lifecycle. To this end, technical KPIs (numerical evaluable) were developed.

The definition of the KPIs followed the multi-stage methodology outlined below in Figure 3.1, while the technical development of the same KPIs was based on the S.M.A.R.T. framework, explained in Figure 3.2.

In addition, given the relevant number of KPIs identified, they have been ranked on a scale from 0 (Low-Priority) to 2 (High-Priority) to:

- Focus the attention of all partners, including the pilots, on the main objectives of the project, considering the uncertainties arising from the initial phase of the project;
- Identify the most relevant KPIs from the complete list proposed to determine which KPIs could be used to define the baseline performance and the initial monitoring plan of each pilot;
- "Penalise" the most complex indicators that are sensitive to variables over which there is little or no control.

The development of the KPIs considered the Sustainable Development Goals (SDG) documentation and, as far as possible, was aligned with the Built4People initiative (European Commission, WILSON Partners, 2024) and other European projects developed in the same field.

Figure 3.1: Multi-stage methodology approach

The S.M.A.R.T. framework was chosen from the various frameworks available in the literature to address the need to identify technical and measurable performance indicators.

It denotes that all KPIs must be:

- **Specific:** KPIs must be clear and specific, able to quantify the specific objectives of innovation;
- **Measurable:** KPIs must be able to be scientifically measured and monitored over time;
- **Achievable:** KPIs must capture realistic and achievable goals;
- **Relevant:** KPIs must be relevant to support decision-making processes based on a sustainable building life cycle approach;
- **Time based:** KPIs need to be measured in relation to a specific time horizon. Each KPI can potentially have a specific reference period (daily, monthly, seasonal, or annual processing frequency).

Figure 3.2: S.M.A.R.T. Framework

3.1. Summary of the main assumptions in the deliverable

Below are the main assumptions that were considered for the development of this deliverable:

1. Analysis of all INNs proposed in the project, including the three innovations in cluster 1. These are important to be considered as they form the basis of the whole project (decentralised data infrastructure) and influence the availability of data required by the more building-related INNs.
2. Given the relevant number of KPIs, the most important ones were identified and linked to the different pilots, according to their characteristics, their actual status, and the information available at this early stage of the project. This was done in order to define a possible initial set of baseline indicators and an initial monitoring plan.
3. The remaining indicators listed in the "Panel of KPIs" should be considered as additional indicators that can be selected during the upcoming implementation and monitoring phases to assess the specificities of each pilot, to evaluate the performance of the WILSON solutions and the achieved energy and non-energy performances.

Finally, a conservative and flexible approach is proposed, with the aim of revising the indicators as the project progresses, sensors are installed, and the various innovations are developed.

4. BUILDING LIFE CYCLE PHASES AND LINKS WITH WILSON “SUITE OF SOLUTIONS”

The WILSON project aims to build a decentralised data architecture for building and district digital twinning, which allows to improve the performance of buildings, both in terms of energy and non-energy, over their entire life cycle. For this reason, it is crucial to analyse the different phases of a building’s life cycle and understand how the developed INNs interact with all or some of them, particularly focusing on data flow.

In section 4.1, all phases of the life cycle of a building are described, from design to demolition, following the main standards currently in force. Then, in section 4.2, a technical overview is presented on the contribution that each INN developed in the WILSON environment can make in the different phases.

The analysis aims to identify links between innovations and life cycle stages, highlighting how and when it will be possible to assess the positive effects of proposed solutions. The result of this activity is summarized in Table 4.21.

4.1. Building Life Cycle Phases

There are at least 4 different phases (or stages) in the life cycle of a building. These phases are clearly and technically presented in the main reference documents for conducting an LCA assessment for a Building: the Product Category Rules PCR 2019:14 for Construction Products (EPD International AB) and the Complementary Product Category Rules C-PCR-029 for Buildings (EPD International AB). These documents are, of course, aligned with the main standards for the building environments, such as EN 15804:2012, the EN 15941:2024, and the ISO21930:2017.

The life cycle phases of a building, as outlined in the aforementioned references, can be summarized as follows:

1. **Product Phase:** this stage includes all the upstream phases of an LCA Assessment, including the supply of raw materials, the transport and the production of ancillary materials, pre-products, products, co-products, and packaging (EPD International AB).
2. **Construction Phase:** this phase covers the construction of the building and includes all the environmental impacts associated with the transport of materials, products, and construction equipment to and from the site, construction and installation activities, and finally, the management of construction waste (EPD International AB).
3. **Use Phase:** this phase covers the environmental impacts associated with the regular use of a building. It takes into account not only the impacts related to the energy demand of the building’s technical systems and water consumption, but also the environmental impacts associated with the regular use of the building (e.g. continuous emissions from materials in the house, materials from the façade, etc.), the impacts of maintenance and repair activities, replacement and refurbishment operations (EPD International AB).
4. **End of Life Phase:** this phase starts when the building is decommissioned, and no further use is foreseen. The phase considers activities such as deconstruction and

demolition, transport for disposal of discarded materials, reuse, recovery, or recycling of waste or, in the worst case, waste disposal (EPD International AB).

All this information is also clearly presented in Figure 4.1.

Figure 4.1: System diagram illustrating the processes that are included in the product system, divided into life-cycle stages and information modules (EPD International AB)

In addition to the four phases of the building life cycle described above, the **design phase**, where the technical design of buildings and building solutions is developed, has also been considered in the definition of the KPIs, especially when considering the design of renovation or refurbishment.

4.2. WILSON Suite of Solutions

The WILSON Project proposes a “Suite of Solutions” consisting of 9 different innovations (INNs) plus an additional Planning Investment Tool, defined as Key Exploitable Result (KER) for the techno-economic assessment of the planned actions and improvements. Since each INN has its own environment and objectives, it is essential at this point of the narrative to clearly understand the focus of each INN and its impact on the building life cycle.

The technical details of each INN (e.g. general description, expected benefits, input, output, and main requirements) plus the corresponding building life cycle phases it affects were studied and investigated in collaboration with the tool developers through a tailored questionnaire. All the relevant information provided in the questionnaires are presented in the tables below.

4.2.1. INNI – 3: Data and Interoperability Toolset

Below, the key aspect of each INN related to cluster 1, named “**Data and Interoperability**” are reported:

Table 4.1: INNI – General Information

INNI: District Digital Twins: federation and data mesh approach	
General description:	The proposed federation and data mesh approach for district digital twins aims to enhance interoperability and standardize data integration while maintaining autonomy and supporting the enrichment of the interconnected data.
Focus of the INN:	The federation and data mesh approach focuses on developing a district DT information management framework that enables the prototyping of district-level DTs based on a data mesh architecture, considering data openness and autonomy. It supports decentralized federated data modelling and pre-existing ontologies to improve interoperability and integration with existing and future tools and data sets.
Expected benefits:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Improved data accessibility and availability; • Support decentralized data ownership; • Integration of various data types for Digital Twinning (BIM, GIS, IoT, BMS, maintenance records).
Data elaborated by the INN (input data):	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Digital twin datasets: BIM data, GIS data, IoT data, BMS data, maintenance records.
Output of the INN:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • N/A – The data mesh approach acts as an underpinning technical layer to provide federation for all the data sets, solutions and use cases developed in the WILSON project.
Main requirements of the INN:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Deployment of federated data network architecture.

Table 4.2: INNI – Building Life Cycle Phases

Building Life Cycle Phases vs INNI		
[X]	Design Phase	The federation and data mesh approach underpins the development of the different INNs and use cases across the whole lifecycle of buildings.
[X]	Product Phase	
[X]	Construction Phase	
[X]	Use Phase (including Maintenance and Refurbishment)	
[X]	End of Life Phase	

Table 4.3: INN2 – General Information

INN2: Personalised Building Data Hubs (PDHs)	
General description:	Personalized Data Hubs (PDHs) are digital hubs, one per building, which function as public interface points from which building data about a particular building can be retrieved by any other agent, thus providing different data access depending on the agent's identity. The PDHs adhere to International Data Space (IDS) principles. They provide real-time asset data to all interested stakeholders (building owners, tenants, etc.), improving user experience and data management and reuse.
Focus of the INN:	The Personalised Building Data Hubs (PDH) focus on providing every type of building data available for the specific building (e.g. point clouds, 3D, BIM, telemetry, documents, building specifications and building ownership). In addition, the service provided by INN2 offers identity-based access control.
Expected benefits:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provision of relevant data specific to the building that can be used in downstream LCA-oriented solutions.
Data elaborated by the INN (input data):	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • BIM models in native file format (e.g. Revit, ArchiCAD, Tekla); • IFC files in Design Transfer (DTV) or Reference View (RV); • IoT streams, which are connection parameters to locally available IoT data streams; • Documents, e.g. PDFs, JPEGs, and PNGs, about the building or specific parts of the building; • Point cloud models, e.g. LAS, E57, PCD files that represent the building or individual parts of the building; • Mapping table which links each IoT stream, point cloud model, and document to a specific ID of the building or of an element of the building.
Output of the INN:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • BIM models potentially uploaded; • IFC files potentially uploaded; • IoT streams potentially uploaded; • Documents potentially uploaded; • Point cloud models potentially uploaded.
Main requirements of the INN:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Availability of data, models, and information; • Ability to export data in the original format; • High quality data;

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Implementation of PDH, including API interfaces.
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Table 4.4: INN2 – Building Life Cycle Phases

Building Life Cycle Phases vs INN2		
[X]	Design Phase	During the design phase, the building's PDH is prepared and progressively filled.
[]	Product Phase	N/A
[X]	Construction Phase	During the construction phase, the PDH is updated to represent the latest version of what is being built. For each element, an as-built state is recorded (IFC representation, object-specific point cloud, and other relevant documentation).
[X]	Use Phase (including Maintenance and Refurbishment)	<p>In the use stage, the PDH collects all data about a building, including telemetry and real-time data (sensor stream and actuators). The data is made available through APIs built on a data lake that includes a graph database, IoT data streams, BIM models, and other files or documents. The PDH data is used for maintenance planning and recording.</p> <p>In refurbishment or renovation projects, the PDH data can be consulted to obtain the latest state of the building, particularly its original BIM data, its geometry and potentially available maintenance data.</p>
[X]	End of Life Phase	During the demolition and end-of-life phase, the building elements, and therefore the information contained in the PDH, are broken down into smaller elements. The reused elements are accompanied by the data from the previous PDH to create a material passport that travels with them. The building's PDH is also stored in a neutral instance as a form of long-term archiving.

Table 4.5: INN3 – General Information

INN 3: P2P data and services marketplace (blockchain-based)	
General description:	The P2P data and services marketplace consists of an extensible and decentralised framework that leverages blockchain and smart contracts to overcome the limitations of data mesh architectures by automating governance processes such as enforcing data access and usage, maintaining quality standards, and ensuring regulatory compliance. This approach enables seamless integration between service providers, building owners and stakeholders, facilitating secure and efficient transactions while preserving data ownership.
Focus of the INN:	The focus of the P2P Data and Services Marketplace is to develop an extensible and decentralised framework in which users, service providers and other stakeholders can participate in transactions of data and services and be remunerated accordingly.
Expected benefits:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Improve efficiency and transparency throughout the building lifecycle; • Improve data security; • Standardise data governance processes.
Data elaborated by the INN (input data):	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • N/A, the INN must accept the data sent by other innovations, which is yet to be defined.
Output of the INN:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • N/A, the platform will function as a communication channel between INNs, ensuring that the content of the input data remains unchanged. In addition, the platform will verify the validity, consistency, and compliance with established data governance policies. This includes ensuring that the data conforms to expected formats, maintains internal consistency, and meets all standards. Only after these checks, the data will be distributed across the blockchain network, ensuring seamless and compliant data integration between developed innovations.
Main requirements of the INN:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Deployment of blockchain platform; • High quality data.

Table 4.6: INN3 – Building Life Cycle Phases

Building Life Cycle Phases vs INN3		
[X]	Design Phase	This INN acts as a communication channel between all the innovations promoted within the WILSON environment, so it will be linked to all phases of the building life cycle.
[X]	Product Phase	
[X]	Construction Phase	
[X]	Use Phase (including Maintenance and Refurbishment)	
[X]	End of Life Phase	

4.2.2. INN4 – 5: Planning and Management Toolset

Below, the key aspect of each INN related to cluster 2, named “**Planning and Management Toolset**,” are reported:

Table 4.7: INN4 – General Information

INN 4: Semantic-aware analytics energy management toolset	
General description:	The energy management analysis toolset aims to promote the optimisation of the energy flows of a building and its strategic assets, reduce energy consumption, and guarantee efficiency and user comfort. In addition, the INN aims to guide stakeholders, through a DSS (Decision Support System) service, in identifying the best energy and flexibility strategies.
Focus of the INN:	The INN is focused on optimising the overall performance (energy, comfort, RES, etc.) of the building during normal use.
Expected benefits:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reduction in energy consumption; • Reduction in GHG emissions (Greenhouse Gas Emissions); • Improvement of energy efficiency of assets and building; • Improvement of comfort conditions.
Data elaborated by the INN (input data):	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Energy-intensive asset data (HVAC and lighting operating data, occupancy trends, and comfort conditions); • Building data (real-time data from asset and historical data); • Thermal loss profile and Meteorological data; • Building flexibility forecasting.
Output of the INN:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Energy consumption, production, and price curves; • Occupancy and thermal profiling; • Energy self-consumption and price optimisation; • Fault and overload optimisation.
Main requirements of the INN:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Building data available and updated (DT model, geometry, energy consumption in real time and forecast); • Reliable external weather data and thermo-hygrometric parameters; • On-site monitoring sensors.

Table 4.8: INN4 – Building Life Cycle Phases

Building Life Cycle Phases vs INN4		
[]	Design Phase	N/A
[]	Product Phase	N/A
[]	Construction Phase	N/A
[X]	Use Phase (including Maintenance and Refurbishment)	The INN focuses on the day-to-day operations with the aim of optimizing energy use through data-based strategies.
[]	End of Life Phase	N/A

Table 4.9: INN5 – General Information

INN 5: CIMBA: predictive maintenance	
General description:	CIMBA is a predictive maintenance tool based on collective intelligence from homogenous assets within the building portfolio. It aims to train asset degradation models, accomplished through the fusion of datasets obtained from multiple buildings within a portfolio. Degradation and failure data are rare for building assets, and different types of defects show distinguishing characteristics. Hence, individual assets do not exhibit the entirety of these defects. CIMBA addresses this through the concept of transfer learning.
Focus of the INN:	Operation and use phase of buildings, and in particular, Maintenance of critical building assets.
Expected benefits:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reduced unplanned downtime and corresponding emergency repairs; • Optimised maintenance scheduling and reduced unnecessary routine checks; • Minimise potential interruptions through planning repairs and replacements during non-peak hours; • Reduced risks of failure that might compromise the safety of occupants and regulatory compliances; • Make more informed decisions about maintaining and managing assets with real-time data and analytics.
Data elaborated by the INN (input data):	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Technical functioning parameters of each critical asset (below some examples): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Boiler: inlet and outlet water temperature, flowrate, pressure, fuel consumption rates, maintenance logs; ○ Pump: vibration, flowrate, pressure, noise level, maintenance logs; ○ Radiators and heating coil: inlet and outlet temperature, flowrate, pressure, surface temperature, maintenance logs; ○ Fan: vibration and noise, speed (RPM) readings, maintenance logs.
Output of the INN:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Maintenance scheduling and prioritisation plan.
Main requirements of the INN:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Existing asset data records, including list of critical assets;

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • IoT sensor and BMS data; • Historical maintenance data.
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Table 4.10: INN5 – Building Life Cycle Phases

Building Life Cycle Phases vs INN5		
[]	Design Phase	N/A
[]	Product Phase	N/A
[]	Construction Phase	N/A
[X]	Use Phase (including Maintenance and Refurbishment)	The predictive maintenance tool provides data-driven maintenance scheduling that helps determine the best time to repair and replace assets and the operational condition of these assets.
[]	End of Life Phase	N/A

4.2.3. INN6 – 7: Environmental performance Toolset

Below, the key aspect of each INNs related to cluster 3, named “**Environmental performances Toolset**,” are reported.

Table 4.11: INN6 – General Information

INN 6: HIBOU: biodiversity & Nature Based Solutions (NBS) in the urban systems	
General description:	The HIBOU methodology and toolset assess the interaction between urban systems, the nature-based solutions and biodiversity according to an integrated approach, considering LCA, ecological expertise and data analysis. This solution makes it possible to assess the impact of buildings and urban systems in terms of climate change, local (in situ) and global (ex situ) biodiversity loss and urban heat island mitigation (UHI).
Focus of the INN:	The aim of HIBOU tool is to provide an integrated assessment of the biodiversity, ecosystem services and climate change of an urban system to help stakeholders make the most environmentally sound urban planning decisions.
Expected benefits:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Environmental assessment based on an integrated approach of climate change mitigation, biodiversity, and climate change adaptation; Decision support based on quantitative performance indicators; Considering both local and global impacts of the building and urban project to avoid shifting pressures/impacts.
Data elaborated by the INN (input data):	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Building type, roof typology, geometric data and surfaces, construction materials for building components, thermal and optical characteristics of urban surfaces; Land use occupation (according to the BAFh nomenclature); Meteorological data; Ecological inventories, Typologies, and characteristics of vegetation types; Detailed footprints of the urban environment (buildings, outdoor spaces, etc.).
Output of the INN:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Carbon footprint assessment (both at buildings and urban systems level); <i>In-situ</i> and <i>ex-situ</i> biodiversity assessment; Urban heat island assessment and mitigation.

Main requirements of the INN:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Building data: DT model, geometry, materials, water, and energy consumption; • Reliable external weather data; • Outdoor spaces characteristics and land use occupation.
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Table 4.12: INN6 – Building Life Cycle Phases

Building Life Cycle Phases vs INN6		
[X]	Design Phase	The HIBOU methodology and toolset is based on an integrated approach including the LCA and integrates all the stages of the life cycle of a building/urban development project, in accordance with the European standards specific to the building LCA (EN 15804 and EN 15978), and other collaborative initiatives in order to consider the local impacts.
[X]	Product Phase	
[X]	Construction Phase	
[X]	Use Phase (including Maintenance and Refurbishment)	
[X]	End of Life Phase	

Table 4.13: INN7 – General Information

INN 7: CONTINIUM: centralised data repository for material passport	
General description:	<p>Continium is a centralised data repository designed to support the different phases of a building's life cycle. It can store data extracted from documents (e.g. the semantic model of the building) as well as data generated by engineering tools and devices.</p> <p>In addition, the tool can function as a digital twin of engineering tools, providing access to the relevant building input data needed to perform the intended calculations.</p> <p>In this perspective, the tool is not a traditional engineering tool for input and output description, but an enabling system that facilitates the monitoring of the building description and its indicators.</p>
Focus of the INN:	<p>The focus of the Continium platform is to provide a robust and scalable solution for managing building data throughout its lifecycle. By centralising data, facilitating integration and ensuring accessibility, it empowers stakeholders to make informed decisions and optimise operations.</p>
Expected benefits:	<p>Maintain building data extracted from auditing data and documents, maintain BIM and materials database information for accurate calculation of material passports & performance indicators.</p>
Data elaborated by the INN (input data):	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • BIM files; audits collected information and forms.
Output of the INN:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Evaluation of data completeness. • Evaluation of data quality; • Storage of external-services-calculated building-related KPIs; • Storage of material passports.
Main requirements of the INN:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Building data (DT model, geometry, materials, water and energy consumption, connexion to material Databases, collection of initial situation audits data);

Table 4.14: INN7 – Building Life Cycle Phases

Building Life Cycle Phases vs INN7		
[X]	Design Phase	The Continium platform can function as a central repository of data and is, therefore, applicable to all phases of the building lifecycle. It is constantly updated based on the evolution of the building.
[X]	Product Phase	
[X]	Construction Phase	
[X]	Use Phase (including Maintenance and Refurbishment)	
[X]	End of Life Phase	

4.2.4. INN8 – 9: Building Diagnostics Toolset

Below, the key aspect of each INNs related to cluster 4, named “**Building Diagnostics Toolset**,” are reported.

Table 4.15: INN8 – General Information

INN 8: Risk and resilience of the built environment	
General description:	The INN proposes a risk and resilience-based approach that integrates resilience capabilities (Plan/Prepare, Detect, Absorb, Recover, Adapt) into the asset management cycle (Plan/Assess, Design, Build, Manage and Maintain) to identify mitigation strategies and ensure swift recovery from the minimum performance level by optimizing the recovery process.
Focus of the INN:	The aim of the INN is to integrate risk and resilience analysis of buildings and building portfolios into asset management to provide key information such as the resilience of the asset, an assessment of potential losses if corrective action is not taken, and to help stakeholders make more informed decisions.
Expected benefits:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Designing solutions (renovation and refurbishment actions) to increase the resilience of the asset to climatic hazards; Increase the useful life of the asset.
Data elaborated by the INN (input data):	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Building specifications (Details about the building's structure, materials, and design); Environmental data (Information on local climate conditions, weather patterns, and potential environmental hazards); Operational data (Data on building usage, occupancy rates, and maintenance schedules); Data to be integrated into the tool should be provided through the standard file formats currently used by geographic computer systems (e.g. CSV files, shapefile files for vector type geometry data, and GeoTIFF files for raster data)
Output of the INN:	The INN could potentially generate comprehensive reports and actionable insight, including: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Risk Assessment Report, which consists of an evaluation of the current risk levels and potential vulnerabilities of the building); Resilience Improvement Plan, with recommendations for enhancing the resilience

	of the building through specific actions and strategies; <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cost-Benefit Analysis, which is an analysis of the financial implications of proposed resilience measures, including potential savings and return on investment.
Main requirements of the INN:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Building data available and updated (DT model, geometry); • Availability of climate hazard historical data.

Table 4.16: INN8 – Building Life Cycle Phases

Building Life Cycle Phases vs INN8		
[X]	Design Phase	The INN influences the design phases of the proposed to-be solution to encourage and guide the stakeholder towards the most resilient solution, or the solution that helps the building to be less vulnerable to external events.
[]	Product Phase	N/A
[]	Construction Phase	N/A
[X]	Use Phase (including Maintenance and Refurbishment)	The INN assesses the risk and resilience level of the as-is building, e.g. during the ordinary use phase. In this phase, maintenance and refurbishment stages are also considered and influenced by the INN8.
[]	End of Life Phase	N/A

Table 4.17: INN9 – General Information

INN 9: BIM-enabled Smart Readiness Indicator Calculator	
General description:	<p>The BIM-enabled Smart Readiness Indicator Calculator for buildings, which promotes the interoperability between stakeholders, allows the assessment of the performance of the building itself (e.g. the building's response to itself, the building's response to the network, and the building's response to the user's needs) according to the data available in BIM models.</p> <p>In fact, the use of BIM data makes it easier to share, access, and manage building information across different systems and stakeholders involved. This interconnected approach ensures that the Smart Readiness Indicator (SRI) can be smoothly integrated into the overall assessment of the building's energy performance.</p> <p>The approach proposed in this solution (INN9) has many advantages, such as data interoperability, efficient and time-saving assessment of building performance, use of accurate and detailed data (inputs and outputs) and standardised assessment.</p>
Focus of the INN:	<p>The aim of the INN is to automatically estimate the SRI score of a building, based on data retrieved from BIM documents, to promote the digitisation of buildings and the adoption of smart technologies with a focus on the automation, monitoring, and improvement of technical building systems to improve energy efficiency.</p>
Expected benefits:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Time-saving building performance assessment driven by BIM Models; • Building digitalisation and automation to promote efficiency during the use phase; • Data interoperability and standardised evaluation.
Data elaborated by the INN (input data):	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • BIM-related input data: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ General building information (i.e. typology, location, floor area, construction year and building state); ○ Technical domains present (Heating; DHW; Cooling; Ventilation; Electricity consumption); ○ RES applicability (storage and production);

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Energy carriers (electricity and non-electricity) and district heating availability; ○ Service applicability and main functionality level. • Building operations input data: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Total energy consumption (kWh) and electric and non-electric carrier; ○ Electric energy consumption from HVAC for Heating, cooling, and ventilation (kWh), for DHW (kWh); ○ Total electric consumption (kWh); ○ PV generation (kWh). • Domain and impact weightings input data: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Domain weighting factors for Heating, DHW, Cooling, Ventilation and Electricity consumption for residential and non-residential (BSO); ○ Impact weightings to 7 criteria for residential and non-residential (BSO), including, (Energy efficiency; Energy flexibility & storage; Comfort; Convenience; Health, well-being, and accessibility; Maintenance and fault prediction; Info to occupants.
Output of the INN:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Score key 1 "Energy savings and operation" (% from 0 to 1); • Score key 2 "Building respond to the occupant needs" (% from 0 to 1); • Score key 3 "Energy flexibility" (% from 0 to 1); • Total SRI score rate (% from 0 to 1).
Main requirements of the INN:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • BIM related and building operations input data, and domain and impact, as previously detailed.

Table 4.18: INN9 – Building Life Cycle Phases

Building Life Cycle Phases vs INN9		
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Design Phase	The INN provides a powerful means to evaluate the impacts of building smartification on energy flexibility. By leveraging data from smart building systems, automation, and energy management tools, the innovation can assess how effectively a building can adapt its energy consumption patterns in response to changing conditions.
<input type="checkbox"/>	Product Phase	N/A
<input type="checkbox"/>	Construction Phase	N/A
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Use Phase (including Maintenance and Refurbishment)	<p>The INN assesses building performance in several areas, including renewable energy integration, demand response, energy flexibility and the ability to reduce energy consumption by adapting to occupancy patterns and external weather conditions. The SRI calculated by the INN plays an important role in improving building maintenance by promoting smarter, automated, and more efficient systems. Buildings with higher SRI scores are easier to maintain and operate more efficiently.</p> <p>Finally, the solution helps to assess the impact of retrofits on a building's smart capabilities, helping stakeholders to plan cost-effectively. Investments in smart technologies driven by the INN ensure both financial and operational benefits, with higher SRI scores indicating greater efficiency, adaptability, and sustainability.</p>
<input type="checkbox"/>	End of Life Phase	N/A

4.2.5. KER10: Investment Planning Tool

Below, the key aspect of WILSON Investment Tool are reported.

Table 4.19: KER10 – General Information

KER 10: Investment Planning Tool	
General description:	The investment tool will support the decision-making process of investors and integrate technical factors (such as energy efficiency improvements, reduced operational costs, etc) with economic ones (such as increased property value, associated up-front expenses), providing stakeholders with comprehensive insights to support their decision-making processes regarding operations and planned investments. The investment tool will support the development of new business models. The tool will target a wide audience of sustainable energy investors, boosting the project's reach even post-completion.
Focus of the INN:	The focus of the investment planning tool is to perform a techno-economic assessment of the proposed solution, guide decision makers towards the most effective one, and evaluate how these improvements affect the value of the building itself.
Expected benefits:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reduction in carbon emissions and environmental impact; • Improved energy efficiency and operational cost savings; • Enhanced property value and alignment with green finance standards.
Data elaborated by the INN (input data):	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Historical energy consumption data; • Historical energy costs data (EUR); • Maintenance and operational cost records (OPEX, EUR); • Investment cost (CAPEX, EUR) data; • Energy consumption prediction data; • Maintenance and operational cost prediction data (OPEX2, EUR); • Expected revenue (EUR); • Environmental impact metrics (e.g. GHG emissions (Scope 1 data, Scope 2 data, Scope 3 data)).
Output of the INN:	The main outputs of the tool are financial and environmental metrics, including: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ROI and payback period calculations; • Cost saving projections;

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Environmental impact assessments (e.g. carbon emissions reduction); • Financial models for investment scenarios.
Main requirements of the INN:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Economic data on investments undertaken; • Performance (energy and environmental) of buildings before and after refurbishment; • Costs of energy sources.

Table 4.20: KER10 – Building Life Cycle Phases

Building Life Cycle Phases vs KER10		
[X]	Design Phase	The tool can assist stakeholders in the financial and economic assessment of renovation activities during their design phase.
[]	Product Phase	N/A
[]	Construction Phase	N/A
[X]	Use Phase (including Maintenance and Refurbishment)	The tool focuses on supporting sustainable energy related investment decision making, optimizing energy and financial performance during operation, and guiding renovation decisions.
[]	End of Life Phase	N/A

The Table 4.21 reports the screening of the mapping analysis.

Table 4.21: Mapping of the correlation between Building Phases and Tools

Building Life Cycle Phases	INN1	INN2	INN3	INN4	INN5	INN6	INN7	INN8	INN9	KER10
Design Phase	X	X	X			X	X	X	X	X
Product Phase	X		X			X	X			
Construction Phase	X	X	X			X	X			
Use Phase (including Maintenance and Refurbishment)	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
End of Life Phase	X	X	X			X	X			

5. LIFE CYCLE ORIENTED INDICATORS PANEL (PANEL OF KPIS)

Chapter 5, which is the core section of this report, presents the list of WILSON KPIs, referred to as the “Panel of KPIs” (Section 5.1), as well as the list of selected contingency KPIs (Section 5.2).

Before introducing the panel itself, the chapter provides a concise overview of its structure and key outcomes, serving as a practical guide for its application during the upcoming phases of the project.

The KPIs were organized by innovation clusters and macro themes studied.

For each KPI, the following information was provided:

- KPI code and name;
- Construction phase (among those reported in chapter 4.1) and application level (pilot, building, asset, etc.);
- KPI description;
- Unit of measurement and monitoring frequency;
- Required data, calculation method and baseline for comparison;
- Additional comments and requirements;
- Priority level.

The high-priority KPIs take precedence in this first phase evaluation due to the relevant number of indicators proposed. They can also be used to assess the baseline performance of each pilot project, as proposed in Chapter 6. It is important to remember that the prioritisation, as well as the assignment of KPIs to each pilot, has been done with the contribution of both technical partners and pilot references.

The remaining indicators of lower priority have been reported to encourage discussion among project partners and, where possible, to assess the specificities of pilots and use cases that could be monitored in the next phase of implementation and evaluation.

A total of 80 KPIs were developed. Among these:

- 5 KPIs are generic and applicable to the WILSON Project and Pilots as they relate to data quality and completeness.
- 12 KPIs were identified for Cluster 1, entitled “Data and Interoperability Toolset”.
- 39 KPIs were identified for Cluster 2, entitled “Planning and Management Toolset”.
- 9 KPIs were identified for Cluster 3, entitled “Environmental Performance Toolset”.
- 10 KPIs were identified for Cluster 4, entitled “Building Diagnostics Toolset”.
- 5 KPIs were identified for the Investment Planning Tool.

Of these, 30 KPIs were given the highest priority, while 6 were considered as high-priority contingency KPIs. Additional contingency KPIs may be identified from the remaining list of lower priority indicators.

The proposed KPIs cover a wide range of themes and can be used in the next implementation, monitoring, and demonstration strategy, including:

- Energy Efficiency and Renewable Energy;
- Energy Performance, SRI, and Energy Storage;
- Predictive Maintenance;
- Climate Change, Biodiversity and Urban Heat Island;
- Comfort and Ventilation System;
- Data and Services Marketplace;
- Data Quality, Data Storage & Data Completeness;
- EV Infrastructure and Microgrid Optimisation;
- PDHs, Scalability and Replicability;
- Techno-economic Investment.

5.1. Panel of KPIs

Section 5.1 comprises the main activity of this deliverable, as it lists the KPIs identified and provides a description and technical information for each of them. The last column shows the priority level associated with each KPI. The aim of the panel is to identify the main KPIs that can be evaluated or potentially evaluated once the implementation phase starts, in order to assess the performance of buildings and assets in terms of both energy and non-energy use.

5.1.1. General and Pilot Common KPIs

Table 5.1 **Error! Reference source not found.** shows five different high-level KPIs developed to assess the scalability and replicability of the project, the synergies developed, and the quality of the analyses and activities conducted within the project. KPIs 1 and 2 have been included to assess the success of the project and the achievement of the objectives set out in the Grant Agreement, while KPIs 3, 4 and 5 apply to all pilot sites to assess the state of completeness and quality of the data that will populate the digital twin models. Indeed, for the purposes of the project, it is extremely important to have complete, high-quality digital models.

Table 5.1: General and Pilot Common KPIs

Code	KPI Preview	Main Topic	Building Phase	Level of Application	KPI Description	U.m.	Data Requested	Monitoring Frequency	Calculation Method	Baseline and benchmark	Notes and Requirements	Priority
KPI 1	Scalability and Replicability	Scalability and Replicability	All	WILSON PROJECT	The KPI quantify the number of Business Models developed within WILSON Project and their replicability.	Dimensionless (-)	Number of Business Models developed and tested.	Year	Scalability and Replicability = \sum Business Models	9 (as reported in the agreement)	None	1
KPI 2	Synergy index	Scalability and Replicability	All	WILSON PROJECT	The KPI quantifies the number of synergies with other projects.	Dimensionless (-)	Number of established synergies.	Year	Synergy index = \sum number of projects for which synergies have been established	15 (as reported in the agreement)	None	1
KPI 3	Data Completeness (mandatory data)	Data Completeness	All	Pilot Site & Building level	The KPI measures the percentage of mandatory data required to develop a digital twin model faithful to the demonstration site. To calculate the completeness of the model, ad hoc databases will be created on the characteristics of the demonstration sites, including both structural information (geometries, materials, integrated equipment, etc.) and energy and environmental information. A monitoring plan will make it possible to evaluate the improvement of the data collection activities.	Ratio (%)	The data required for the assessment of the indicators will be requested and collected in a dedicated database (Data Collection Checklist), which will be further developed to include energy and non-energy information. The information will be available in WP4 and WP9/10.	Month, Year	Completeness of data (mandatory data) = number of mandatory fields to describe the building filled in / number of fields provided to describe the pilot	100%	The pilot sites' contact persons will have to fill in the checklist indicating the availability of the data and their format. This checklist should be updated monthly or whenever new data are entered, or substantial changes are made to the site and its perimeter.	2
KPI 4	Data Completeness (optional data)	Data Completeness	All	Pilot Site & Building level	The KPI measures the percentage of optional data to be integrated into the digital twin of the demonstration site. To calculate the completeness of the model, ad hoc databases will be created on the characteristics of the demonstration sites, including both structural information (geometries, materials, integrated equipment, etc.) and energy and environmental information. A monitoring plan will make it possible to evaluate the improvement of the data collection activities.	Ratio (%)	The data required for the assessment of the indicators will be requested and collected in a dedicated database (Data Collection Checklist), which will be further developed to include energy and non-energy information. The information will be available in WP4 and WP9/10.	Month, Year	Completeness of data (optional data) = number of optional fields to describe the building filled in / number of fields provided to describe the pilot	None	The pilot sites' contact persons will have to fill in the checklist indicating the availability of the data and their format. This checklist should be updated monthly or whenever new data are entered, or substantial changes are made to the site and its perimeter.	1
KPI 5	Data quality	Data Quality	All	Pilot Site & Building level	The KPI measures the quality of the developed digital twin. To do this, it is proposed to calculate the ratio between the demo-specific data provided via the above-mentioned database and the total data provided (specific data plus generic data/proxies required to perform the analysis, simulations, or assessments). A monitoring plan will make it possible to evaluate the improvement of the data collection activities.	Ratio (%)	The data required for the assessment of the indicators will be requested and collected in a dedicated database (Data Collection Checklist), which will be further developed to include energy and non-energy information. The information will be available in WP4 and WP9/10.	Month, Year	Data Quality = Number of specific data / numbers of provided fields data to describe the pilot	100%	The data quality KPI deals with the % of specific versus generic (default/proxy) data; the more specific the data, the less uncertainty in the results. NB: generic data (by default / proxy) = need to use the default data to run simulations when data is missing.	2

5.1.2. Data and Interoperability Indicators

Table 5.2 **Error! Reference source not found.** below shows the indicators developed in collaboration with the tool developers that can be considered and assessed to evaluate the data and interoperability layer within the WILSON environment. The main topics covered are the availability of data storage, the transmission speed of information and the operation of the data and services marketplace.

Table 5.2: Data and Interoperability Indicators

Code	KPI Preview	Main Topic	Building Phase	Level of Application	KPI Description	U.m.	Data Requested	Monitoring Frequency	Calculation Method	Baseline and benchmark	Notes and Requirements	Priority
KPI 6.1	Availability of data storage (BIM Models)	Data Storage	All	Pilot Site & Building level	This KPI evaluates the availability of data storage for the BIM model database/file storage as a percentage. This metric provides insight into the overall availability and efficient management of storage resources.	Ratio (%)	No data required	Month, Year	Output from INN2 directly in % u.m. Data Storage Availability (%) = (Total Storage Capacity (GB)/Available Storage Capacity (GB)) ×100	None	To calculate this KPI, it is essential to identify and access the specific storage location (e.g., cloud servers, local databases, or distributed storage systems).	1
KPI 6.2	Availability of data storage (IFC Files)	Data Storage	All	Pilot Site & Building level	This KPI evaluates the availability of data storage in the IFC Files database as a percentage. This metric provides insight into the overall availability and efficient management of storage resources.	Ratio (%)	No data required	Month, Year	Output from INN2 directly in % u.m. Data Storage Availability (%) = (Total Storage Capacity (GB)/Available Storage Capacity (GB)) ×100	None	To calculate this KPI, it is essential to identify and access the specific storage location (e.g., cloud servers, local databases, or distributed storage systems).	1
KPI 6.3	Availability of data storage (IoT streams)	Data Storage	All	Pilot Site & Building level	This KPI evaluates the availability of data storage in the IoT Streams database as a percentage. This metric provides insight into the overall availability and efficient management of storage resources.	Ratio (%)	No data required	Month, Year	Output from INN2 directly in % u.m. Data Storage Availability (%) = (Total Storage Capacity (GB)/Available Storage Capacity (GB)) ×100	None	To calculate this KPI, it is essential to identify and access the specific storage location (e.g., cloud servers, local databases, or distributed storage systems).	1
KPI 6.4	Availability of data storage (Documents)	Data Storage	All	Pilot Site & Building level	This KPI evaluates the availability of data storage in the Document Files database as a percentage. This metric provides insight into the overall availability and efficient management of storage resources.	Ratio (%)	No data required	Month, Year	Output from INN2 directly in % u.m. Data Storage Availability (%) = (Total Storage Capacity (GB)/Available Storage Capacity (GB)) ×100	None	To calculate this KPI, it is essential to identify and access the specific storage location (e.g., cloud servers, local databases, or distributed storage systems).	1
KPI 6.5	Availability of data storage (Point Cloud Models)	Data Storage	All	Pilot Site & Building level	This KPI evaluates the availability of data storage in the Point Cloud Models database as a percentage. This metric provides insight into the overall availability and efficient management of storage resources.	Ratio (%)	No data required	Month, Year	Output from INN2 directly in % u.m. Data Storage Availability (%) = (Total Storage Capacity (GB)/Available Storage Capacity (GB)) ×100	None	To calculate this KPI, it is essential to identify and access the specific storage location (e.g., cloud servers, local databases, or distributed storage systems).	1
KPI 7.1	API Slow Response Count (BIM Model)	Transmission speed	All	WILSON PROJECT	This KPI measures the number of interfaces where the response time of the API connected to the BIM model exceeds the pre-defined acceptable threshold.	Dimensionless (-)	No data required	Month, Year	Slow Responses Count=∑ (Response Time >2seconds)	Excellent performance: <= 100 ms Good performance: <= 1 second Acceptable: <= 2 seconds Needs improvement: > 2 seconds	Ensure APIs being tested are under realistic load conditions. For continuous improvement, analyse trends and identify causes of slow responses. PDHs are implemented, including API Interfaces.	1
KPI 7.1	API Slow Response Count (IFC Files)	Transmission speed	All	WILSON PROJECT	This KPI measures the number of interfaces where the response time of the API connected to the IFC files exceeds the pre-defined acceptable threshold.	Dimensionless (-)	No data required	Month, Year	Slow Responses Count=∑ (Response Time >2seconds)	Excellent performance: <= 100 ms Good performance: <= 1 second Acceptable: <= 2 seconds Needs improvement: > 2 seconds	Ensure APIs being tested are under realistic load conditions. For continuous improvement, analyse trends and identify causes of slow responses. PDHs are implemented, including API Interfaces.	1

Code	KPI Preview	Main Topic	Building Phase	Level of Application	KPI Description	U.m.	Data Requested	Monitoring Frequency	Calculation Method	Baseline and benchmark	Notes and Requirements	Priority
KPI 7.1	API Slow Response Count (PDF)	Transmission speed	All	WILSON PROJECT	This KPI measures the number of interfaces where the response time of the API connected to the PDF files exceeds the pre-defined acceptable threshold.	Dimensionless (-)	No data required	Month, Year	Slow Responses Count= \sum (Response Time >2seconds)	Excellent performance: \leq 100 ms Good performance: \leq 1 second Acceptable: \leq 2 seconds Needs improvement: $>$ 2 seconds	Ensure APIs being tested are under realistic load conditions. For continuous improvement, analyse trends and identify causes of slow responses. PDHs are implemented, including API Interfaces.	1
KPI 7.1	API Slow Response Count (Point Cloud Models)	Transmission speed	All	WILSON PROJECT	This KPI measures the number of interfaces where the response time of the API connected to the Point Cloud Models model exceeds the pre-defined acceptable threshold.	Dimensionless (-)	No data required	Month, Year	Slow Responses Count= \sum (Response Time >2seconds)	Excellent performance: \leq 100 ms Good performance: \leq 1 second Acceptable: \leq 2 seconds Needs improvement: $>$ 2 seconds	Ensure APIs being tested are under realistic load conditions. For continuous improvement, analyse trends and identify causes of slow responses. PDHs are implemented, including API Interfaces.	1
KPI 7.1	API Slow Response Count (IoT Streams)	Transmission speed	All	WILSON PROJECT	This KPI measures the number of interfaces where the response time of the API connected to the IoT streams exceeds the pre-defined acceptable threshold.	Dimensionless (-)	No data required	Month, Year	Slow Responses Count= \sum (Response Time >2seconds)	Excellent performance: \leq 100 ms Good performance: \leq 1 second Acceptable: \leq 2 seconds Needs improvement: $>$ 2 seconds	Ensure APIs being tested are under realistic load conditions. For continuous improvement, analyse trends and identify causes of slow responses. PDHs are implemented, including API Interfaces.	1
KPI 8	Number of PDHs Installed	PDHs	All	Building level	The KPI measures the number of PDHs installed within WILSON Project	Dimensionless (-)	Number of PDHs developed and tested.	Month, Year	Number of PDHs installed: \sum PDHs	15 (as reported in the project agreement);	The main requirements of the KPIs are that the PDHs are correctly implemented and tested, including the API interfaces.	2
KPI 9	Peer2Peer communication latency	Data and services marketplace	All	WILSON PROJECT	The KPI measures the time it takes for a message or packet of data to be transmitted from one peer node to another within the blockchain network. The KPI is measured monthly, and its value is compared to a previous average, also calculated monthly, to monitor the value over time.	Milliseconds (ms)	Message reception timestamp: The time when the peer receives a block from another peer. Message send timestamp: The time when the peer has created a block and submitted it to the network.	Month	P2P Latency: mean (peer_mean (Message reception timestamp) - Message send timestamp)	The baseline is the median of the P2P Latency over the past month.	The blockchain platform must be developed and tested. The data required for the assessment of the indicator will be provided by the Tool developers involved in INN3.	2
KPI 10	Organizational network recovery time	Data and services marketplace	All	WILSON PROJECT	This KPI measures the time taken for the network to reorganise after the loss of the peer leader. The KPI is measured every 3 months and its value is compared to a previous average, to monitor the value over time.	Milliseconds (ms)	Organization Network availability: The timestamp when the network has become fully operational and able to process transactions. Peer leader shutdown time: This is the timestamp marking the point when the organization's network has lost its leader peer, thereby becoming dysfunctional.	3 Months	Organizational network recovery Time: mean (organization_mean (Network availability timestamp - Peer leader shutdown time))	The baseline is the median of the ONR Time over the past 3 months.	The blockchain platform must be developed and tested. The data required for the assessment of the indicator will be provided by the Tool developers involved in INN3.	2
KPI 11	Smart contracts latency	Data and services marketplace	All	WILSON PROJECT	The KPI measures the time elapsed between the initiation of a smart contract call and the successful creation of the corresponding transaction on the blockchain. The KPI is measured monthly, and its value is compared to a previous average, also calculated monthly, to monitor the value over time.	Milliseconds (ms)	Transaction creation timestamp: The moment when a transaction is initiated and submitted to the blockchain network. Smart contract execution timestamp: The moment when a smart contract request is created.	Month	Smart contracts latency: mean (Transaction Creation timestamp - Smart contract execution timestamp)	The baseline is the median of the SC Latency over the past month	The blockchain platform must be developed and tested. The data required for the assessment of the indicator will be provided by the Tool developers involved in INN3.	2

Code	KPI Preview	Main Topic	Building Phase	Level of Application	KPI Description	U.m.	Data Requested	Monitoring Frequency	Calculation Method	Baseline and benchmark	Notes and Requirements	Priority
KPI 12	Ordering service recovery time	Data and services marketplace	All	WILSON PROJECT	The KPI measures the time it takes for the network to reorganize after losing the orderer's leader. The KPI is measured every 2 months and its value is compared to a previous average, to monitor the value over time.	Milliseconds (ms)	Network availability: The time when the network is operational and can process transactions. Orderer leader shutdown time: The time when the leader orderer has disconnected thereby, making the ordering service dysfunctional.	2 Months	Ordering service recovery time: mean (Network availability timestamp – orderer leader shutdown time)	The baseline is the median of the SC Latency over the past 2 months	The blockchain platform must be developed and tested. The data required for the assessment of the indicator will be provided by the Tool developers involved in INN3.	1
KPI 13	Active Orderers	Data and services marketplace	All	WILSON PROJECT	The KPI measures the total number of active orderers in the ordering service. Establishing a mode-based baseline for the number of active orderers is useful for identifying anomalies. A sudden drop below this baseline can indicate problems such as node failures or connectivity issues in the ordering service.	Dimensionless (-)	Active orderers: Number of orderers that have received or send a block or a transaction in the last 24 hours.	15 days	Active Orderers: count(active orderers)	The baseline is the mode of active orderers within the ordering service over the past 15 days	The blockchain platform must be developed and tested. The data required for the assessment of the indicator will be provided by the Tool developers involved in INN3.	1
KPI 14	Active Peers	Data and services marketplace	All	WILSON PROJECT	This KPI measures the total number of active peers on the network. Tracking the mode for active peers over a short period of time helps to establish the most common activity levels. Deviations from this baseline can indicate connectivity problems or synchronisation errors.	Dimensionless (-)	Active peers: Number of peers that have received or send a block or a transaction in the last 24 hours.	15 days	Active Peers: count (active peers)	The baseline is the mode of active peers over the past 15 days.	The blockchain platform must be developed and tested. The data required for the assessment of the indicator will be provided by the Tool developers involved in INN3.	1
KPI 15	Active Organizations	Data and services marketplace	All	WILSON PROJECT	The KPI measures the total number of active organizations in the network. Using the mode as a baseline for active organizations provides a clear representation of the most common level of activity within the network.	Dimensionless (-)	Active organizations: Number of organizations that have send or receive a block in at least one of its peers in the last 24 hours.	15 days	Active Organizations: count(active organizations)	The baseline is the mode of active organizations over the past 15 days.	The blockchain platform must be developed and tested. The data required for the assessment of the indicator will be provided by the Tool developers involved in INN3.	1
KPI 16	Peer Synchronization Time	Data and services marketplace	All	WILSON PROJECT	The KPI measures the time it takes for a peer to synchronize with the rest of the peers after a recovery. The KPI is measured every 3 months and its value is compared to a previous average, to monitor the value over time.	Milliseconds (ms)	Peer starts time: The timestamp when a peer becomes operational and ready to establish connection with other peers. Peer availability: The timestamp marking the moment when a peer joins the gossip protocol and begins participating in message dissemination within the organization.	3 Months	Peer Synchronization Time: mean (Peer availability - Peer start time)	The baseline is the median of the PS Time over the past 3 months.	The blockchain platform must be developed and tested. The data required for the assessment of the indicator will be provided by the Tool developers involved in INN3.	1
KPI 17	Orderer Synchronization Time	Data and services marketplace	All	WILSON PROJECT	The KPI measures the time it takes for an orderer to synchronize with the rest of the ordering service after a recovery. The KPI is measured every 2 months and its value is compared to a previous average, to monitor the value over time.	Milliseconds (ms)	Orderer start time: The timestamp when an orderer becomes operational and ready to connect with the ordering service. Orderer availability: The timestamp marking the moment an orderer is	2 Months	Orderer Synchronization Time: mean (Orderer availability – Orderer start time)	The baseline is the median of the OST Time over the past 2 months.	The blockchain platform must be developed and tested. The data required for the assessment of the indicator will be provided by the Tool developers involved in INN3.	1

Code	KPI Preview	Main Topic	Building Phase	Level of Application	KPI Description	U.m.	Data Requested	Monitoring Frequency	Calculation Method	Baseline and benchmark	Notes and Requirements	Priority
							prepared to replicate blocks within the ordering service					

As shown in the table above, KPI family 6 applies to all the pilot sites of the project, while the remaining KPIs assess the performance of WILSON environment in terms of data e service marketplace.

5.1.3. Planning and Management Indicators

Table 5.3 **Error! Reference source not found.** below shows the indicators developed in collaboration with the tool developers that can be considered and assessed to evaluate the energy planning and management of pilots, buildings, assets, and networks. The main topics are density, intensity and efficiency of assets, integration of renewable energy in buildings and storage systems, energy consumption and greenhouse gas emissions, sustainable mobility, stability of distribution networks and predictive maintenance.

Table 5.3: Planning and Management Indicators

Code	KPI Preview	Main Topic	Building Phase	Level of Application	KPI Description	U.m.	Data Requested	Monitoring Frequency	Calculation Method	Baseline and benchmark	Notes and Requirements	Priority
KPI 18	Asset Power Density	Energy Management	Operation	Building level	The KPI measures the ratio between the power of an installed asset (the one under investigation) per unit area. The KPI helps to identify potential improvements in the asset system and to track the reduction in asset power density after renovations/retrofits.	W/m2	Asset Power: the total installed power of the system over a specific area (room, floor, building, etc...); Area: is the specific area over which the asset power is calculated;	Year	Asset Power Density = Total Asset Power for the area of interest (W) / Area of interest (m2).	Asset Power Density (pre WILSON)	To evaluate the indicator, it is important to know the power of the asset or system and the area over which the power density is to be calculated. The area of interest can be a specific room, a house, a floor of a building or the entire building. The KPI is flexible and can be easily adapted to the data available. The data required is design data, both building and of the system.	1
KPI 19	Asset Use Intensity	Energy Management	Operation	Building level	This KPI relates the final energy consumption of an asset or system to the specific reference unit representative of the building's intended use. This indicator helps identify inefficiencies, losses and opportunities for improvement based on occupancy, activity levels and building control. The indicator can potentially be evaluated on a daily, monthly, or annual basis	kWh/ref.un	Asset Energy Consumption (kWh): Total amount of energy consumed by the asset or system under consideration; ref.un: is the reference unit by which the energy consumption is normalised (e.g. the area of a residential building, the number of occupants in a commercial building, the number of beds or patients in a hospital).	Day, Month, Year	Asset Use Intensity = Asset Energy Consumption (kWh) / ref.un	Asset Use Density (pre WILSON) if historical data available and benchmarked against national standards.	The KPI is highly flexible and can be applied to all types of assets within a building, based on available and readily available data. The normalisation factor can be chosen according to the specific needs and intended use of the building, considering that the WILSON project includes buildings with very different characteristics. The demonstration site must select the most appropriate normalisation factor in relation to the intended use of the building (residential, office, hospital, etc.). To evaluate the indicator, it is necessary to install sensors to continuously monitor the performance (energy consumption) of the asset as well as a robust data storage system.	2
KPI 20	HVAC Use Intensity (Winter Season)	Energy Management	Operation	Building level	The KPI measures the final energy consumption of the HVAC system during the heating season per unit area and external weather conditions. The indicator helps to identify low thermal heating efficiency, poor building thermal control or inefficient asset management systems.	kWh/(m2*HDD)	FE Consumption (kWh): EE consumption of the HVAC system during the heating period. Heated Area (m2): Heated area of interest; Heating Degree Days (HDD): calculated considering external weather conditions and national/local regulations.	Month, Year	HVAC Use Intensity (Winter Season) = FE Consumption (kWh) / Heated Area (m2) / Heating Degree Days (HDD)	HVAC Use Density in Winter Season (pre WILSON) if historical data available and benchmarked against national standards.	The KPI helps evaluate the effectiveness of the heating systems and identifies areas where energy consumption is excessive, indicating poor performance of the control systems or high thermal losses. To evaluate the indicator, it is necessary to install sensors to continuously monitor the performance (energy consumption) of the HVAC system, as well as a robust data storage system and an external thermometer capable of providing hourly average outside temperature.	2

Code	KPI Preview	Main Topic	Building Phase	Level of Application	KPI Description	U.m.	Data Requested	Monitoring Frequency	Calculation Method	Baseline and benchmark	Notes and Requirements	Priority
KPI 20	HVAC Use Intensity (Cooling Season)	Energy Management	Operation	Building level	The KPI measures the final energy consumption of the HVAC system during the cooling season per unit area and external weather conditions. The indicator helps to identify low thermal heating efficiency, poor building thermal control or inefficient asset management systems.	kWh/(m ² *CDD)	FE Consumption (kWh): EE consumption of the HVAC system during the cooling period. Cooled Area (m²): Cooled area of interest; Cooling Degree Days (CDD): calculated considering external weather conditions and national/local regulations.	Month, Year	HVAC Use Intensity (Summer Season) = FE Consumption (kWh) / Cooled Area (m ²) / Cooling Degree Days (HDD)	HVAC Use Density in Summer Season (pre WILSON) if historical data available and benchmarked against national standards.	The KPI helps evaluate the effectiveness of the cooling systems and identifies areas where energy consumption is excessive, indicating poor performance of the control systems or high thermal losses. To evaluate the indicator, it is necessary to install sensors to continuously monitor the performance (energy consumption) of the HVAC system, as well as a robust data storage system and an external thermometer capable of providing hourly average outside temperature.	2
KPI 22	Asset Efficiency	Energy Management	Operation	Building level	The KPI evaluates the decrease in final energy consumption of an asset or system. The KPI allows to consider the positive effect of asset management in the overall asset or system energy consumption.	Ratio (%)	Baseline Energy Consumption (kWh) (asset or system) Current Energy Consumption (kWh) (asset or system)	Month, Year	Asset efficiency: (Asset Current Energy Consumption - Asset Baseline Energy Consumption) / Asset Baseline Energy Consumption *100	Asset Efficiency (pre WILSON) if historical data available.	The KPI can be used to monitor the reduction in energy consumption of the asset or system because of optimised management systems or replacement/retrofit. To evaluate the indicator, it is necessary to install sensors to continuously monitor the performance (energy consumption) of the asset as well as a robust data storage system.	1
KPI 23	Heating Comfort Index (HCI) (CARTIF, 2019)	Comfort	Operation	Building level	The KPIs assess the level of discomfort in a room over a reference period by measuring the number of hours the temperature is below the reference threshold.	°C*h	Tcomfort: Setpoint temperature according to national standard and geographical area (considering +/- 1°C as an average deviation); Tactual: hourly average temperature inside a room;	Month	HCI: $\sum (T_{comfort} - T_{actual}) * \Delta time$	None	The KPI can evaluate the effectiveness of the HVAC system and the comfort level of the occupants in the room or building. An occupancy plan is essential for an accurate assessment. To calculate the indicator, it is important to know the setpoint temperatures, the average room temperature, and a robust data storage and processing system capable of linking the average indoor temperature to the time of day.	0
KPI 24	Cooling Comfort Index (CCI) (CARTIF, 2019)	Comfort	Operation	Building level	The KPIs assess the level of discomfort in a room over a reference period, measuring the number of hours the temperature is above the threshold.	°C*h	Tcomfort: Setpoint temperature according to national standard and geographical area (considering +/- 1°C as an average deviation); Tactual: hourly average temperature inside a room;	Week	CCI: $\sum (T_{actual} - T_{comfort}) * \Delta time$	None	The KPI can evaluate the effectiveness of the HVAC system and the comfort level of the occupants in the room or building. An occupancy plan is essential for an accurate assessment. To calculate the indicator, it is important to know the setpoint temperatures, the average room temperature, and a robust data storage and processing system capable of linking the average indoor temperature to the time of day.	0
KPI 25	CO2 Hours Above Acceptable Levels	Comfort	Operation	Building level	The KPI measures the number of minutes during which CO2 concentration exceeds the acceptable limit for human well-being. This limit can be established based on the room's purpose and relevant standards.	hours (h)	CO2 conc, actual: The average CO2 level detected in the room under evaluation, measured over a minute. CO2 lim, max: The maximum threshold value for CO2 concentration.	Month, Year	CO2 Hours: $(\sum (CO2 \text{ conc, actual} - CO2 \text{ lim, max}) * \Delta time) / 60$	None	The KPI evaluates the effectiveness of HVAC operation, particularly in maintaining CO2 concentration below the threshold to ensure occupant comfort and well-being. The KPI can be further modified according to the type of CO2 sensors installed during the WILSON project and the monitoring architecture.	1

Code	KPI Preview	Main Topic	Building Phase	Level of Application	KPI Description	U.m.	Data Requested	Monitoring Frequency	Calculation Method	Baseline and benchmark	Notes and Requirements	Priority
KPI 26	Electricity self-consumption at Building Level (ESC-B) (STRESS, 2018)	Renewable Energy	Operation	Building level	The indicator measures the percentage of locally produced energy that is consumed or stored within the building, relative to the total energy generated locally by the same systems.	Ratio (%)	Locally Consumed Energy (kWh): The amount of energy produced by the renewable systems installed in the building that is directly consumed (or stored). Total Locally Generated Energy (kWh): The total amount of energy generated by the system within the building.	Day, Month, Year	$ESC-B = \frac{\text{Locally consumed energy (el)}}{\text{total locally generated energy (el)}}$	None	The KPI measures the self-consumption of energy at the building level, regardless of the end use of the building. The KPI can potentially be scaled to district level, considering the electricity self-consumption of all buildings. In this case, the requirements and calculation method must be modified. To calculate the indicator, it is necessary to install sensors to monitor the RE that is generated, consumed, stored, and released.	1
KPI 27	Electricity self-sufficiency at Building Level (ESS-B) (STRESS, 2018)	Renewable Energy	Operation	Building level	The KPI measures the ratio between the renewable electricity self-consumed or locally stored within the building and the building's total energy consumption, to assess energy self-sufficiency. The grid energy mix is not considered in this assessment.	Ratio (%)	Locally Consumed Energy: The amount of energy produced by the renewable systems installed in the building that is directly consumed (or stored). Total Energy Consumption: The total amount of energy consumed by the Building during the same period (from all sources, including grid and local generation).	Day, Month, Year	$ESS-B = \frac{\text{Locally consumed energy}}{\text{total energy consumption}}$	None	The indicator measures energy self-sufficiency at the building level, regardless of the final use of the building. To calculate the indicator, it is necessary to install sensors to monitor on-site renewable energy production, energy stored and delivered to the building, and the amount of energy withdrawn from the grid.	1
KPI 28	Share of Renewable at Building Level (SRES-B) (STRESS, 2018)	Renewable Energy	Operation	Building level	The KPI measures the proportion of the building's energy demand that is met by renewable energy sources alone.	Ratio (%)	Energy Demand covered by RES: direct energy used to cover the demand plus renewable energy coming from storage plus renewable energy coming from the grid. Total Energy Consumption: The total amount of energy consumed by the building during the same period (from all sources, including grid and local generation).	Day, Month, Year	$SRES-B = \frac{\text{Energy Demand covered by RES}}{\text{Total Energy Consumption}}$	None	The KPI measures the share of renewable energy at the building level, regardless of the final use of the building. To calculate the indicator, it is necessary to install sensors to monitor onsite RES production, the energy stored and released to the building, the amount of energy withdrawn from the grid with GO, and the total energy demand.	1
KPI 29	Energy Consumption (Usage Phase) (REPORTS, 2021)	Energy Performance	Operation	Pilot Site & Building level	This KPI assesses the total energy consumed by the study object (the entire pilot, an individual building, specific areas of a building) over a specific time horizon. This KPI effectively measures energy performance and facilitates comparison with national and European benchmarks. This indicator also helps to identify priorities for action by comparing final energy consumption between comparable subjects.	kWh/time	Energy Consumption (kWh): The total energy consumed by the subject under study (pilot, single building, specific areas of a building) during its operational phase over a specified period; Time: The reference period used for calculations.	Day, Month, Year	Energy Consumption (Use Phase): Energy Consumption (kWh) / time	Energy Consumption (pre WILSON) if historical data available and benchmarked against national standards.	The KPI measures the energy consumption of the subject over a given period. It is important to install all the sensors necessary to monitor the energy vectors involved in the scope of the analysis, including renewable energy produced/stored (if available), gas consumption and its chemical properties and thermal energy from DHCN.	2
KPI 30	Energy Intensity (Usage Phase)	Energy Performance	Operation	Pilot Site & Building level	This KPI assesses the energy intensity of the study object (the whole pilot, an individual building, specific areas of a building) compared to the specific reference unit representative of the intended use of the subject. This KPI effectively measures energy performance and facilitates comparison with national and European benchmarks. This	kWh/ref.un	Energy Consumption (kWh): The total energy consumed by the subject under study (pilot, single building, specific areas of a building) during its operational phase over a specified period; ref.un: is the reference unit by which the energy consumption is normalised (e.g. the area of a residential building, the	Day, Month, Year	Energy Intensity (Use Phase): Energy Consumption (kWh) / ref.un	Energy intensity (pre WILSON) if historical data available and benchmarked against national standards.	The KPI measures the energy consumption of the subject over a given period. It is important to install all the sensors necessary to monitor the energy vectors involved in the scope of the analysis, including renewable energy produced/stored (if available), gas consumption and its chemical properties and thermal energy from DHCN.	2

Code	KPI Preview	Main Topic	Building Phase	Level of Application	KPI Description	U.m.	Data Requested	Monitoring Frequency	Calculation Method	Baseline and benchmark	Notes and Requirements	Priority
					indicator also helps to identify priorities for action by comparing final energy consumption between comparable subjects.		number of occupants in a commercial building, the number of beds or patients in a hospital).					
KPI 31	Energy Consumption Reduction (Usage Phase)	Energy Performance	Operation	Pilot Site & Building level	The KPI shows the progress in reducing the energy consumption of the subject studied (entire pilot site, individual building, building areas) in relation to the phase of use.	Ratio (%)	Baseline Energy Consumption (kWh) (use phase) Current Energy Consumption (kWh) (use phase)	Month, Year	Energy Consumption Reduction: (Current Energy Consumption - Baseline Energy Consumption) / Baseline Energy Consumption *100	Energy Consumption (pre WILSON) if historical data available.	This KPI measures the reduction in the subject's energy consumption. No additional sensors are required for this KPI as the energy consumption data already required for the previous KPIs is processed. In addition, energy consumption is expected to be reduced by 15% per pilot using the WILSON suite of solutions.	1
KPI 32	Carbon Emissions (Use Phase)	Carbon Emissions	Operation	Pilot Site & Building level	This KPI assesses the amount of CO2 emitted by the study object (the whole pilot, a single building, specific areas of a building) over a given time horizon.	kgCO2/time	Carbon Emissions (kgCO2): The emissions of CO2 by the subject under study (pilot, single building, specific areas of a building) during its operational phase over a specified period; Time: The reference period used for calculations.	Day, Month, Year	Carbon Emissions (Use Phase): carbon Emissions / time	Carbon Emissions (pre WILSON) if historical data available and benchmarked against national standards.	This KPI measures the subject's Carbon Emissions over a given period. No additional sensor is required for this KPI as the energy consumption data already required for the previous KPIs is processed. The extra data required for the calculations are the emission factors of the energy sources used in the building. Use recognised emission factors (standardised values, national values, etc.)	2
KPI 33	Carbon Intensity (Use Phase)	Carbon Emissions	Operation	Pilot Site & Building level	This KPI assesses the carbon Intensity of the study object (the whole pilot, an individual building, specific areas of a building) compared to the specific reference unit representative of the intended use of the subject.	kgCO2/ref.un.	Carbon Emissions (kgCO2): The emissions of CO2 by the subject under study (pilot, single building, specific areas of a building) during its operational phase over a specified period; ref.un: is the reference unit by which the energy consumption is normalised (e.g. the area of a residential building, the number of occupants in a commercial building, the number of beds or patients in a hospital).	Day, Month, Year	Carbon Intensity (Use Phase): Carbon Emissions / ref.un.	Carbon Intensity (pre WILSON) if historical data available and benchmarked against national standards.	The KPI measures the Carbon Intensity of the subject over a given period. No additional sensor is required for this KPI as the energy consumption data already required for the previous KPIs is processed. The extra data required for the calculations are the emission factors of the energy sources used in the building. Use recognised emission factors (standardised values, national values, etc.)	2
KPI 34	Carbon Emission Reduction (Use Phase)	Carbon Emissions	Operation	Pilot Site & Building level	The KPI shows the progress made in reducing the carbon emissions of the subject under study (whole pilot site, individual buildings, building areas) in relation to the phase of use.	Ratio (%)	Baseline Carbon Emissions (kgCO2) (use phase) Current Carbon Emissions (kgCO2) (use phase)	Month, Year	Carbon Emissions Reduction: (Current Carbon Emissions - Baseline Carbon Emissions) / Baseline Carbon Emissions *100	Carbon Emissions (pre WILSON) if historical data available.	This KPI measures the reduction in the subject's carbon emissions. No additional sensors are required for this KPI.	1
KPI 35	Peak Demand Reduction (peak shaving)	Energy Storage System	Operation	Building level	The KPI measures the percentage reduction in a building's peak electricity demand following the implementation of battery storage systems. By analysing energy storage management, it is possible to optimise energy use, resulting in improved efficiency and lower energy costs for the building. The KPI can be analysed over a defined reference period.	Ratio (%)	Building Peak Demand without BESS: The value must be evaluated before the implementation of the energy storage system; Building Peak Demand with BESS: the indicator must be evaluated after the implementation of the energy storage system;	Hour, Day, Month, Year	Peak demand reduction (peak shaving): (Building Peak Demand without BESS - Building Peak demand with BESS) / Building Peak demand without BESS *100	Building peak demand before implementing a storage system (pre-WILSON)	The KPI can be evaluated daily. Post-processing methods can also be used to improve the overall effectiveness of the system. To correctly assess the indicator, it is essential to have access to reliable data on the building's electricity consumption (real time and historical), energy storage system and energy demand curves (daily).	0

Code	KPI Preview	Main Topic	Building Phase	Level of Application	KPI Description	U.m.	Data Requested	Monitoring Frequency	Calculation Method	Baseline and benchmark	Notes and Requirements	Priority
KPI 36	Peak Demand Reduction (cost saving)	Energy Storage System	Operation	Building level	The KPI measures the cost savings achieved by using energy storage systems to reduce the building's peak electricity demand. If the battery is charged using renewable energy, the energy cost is zero. Alternatively, if the battery is charged during off-peak hours, the energy cost is lower, reflecting off-peak grid tariffs.	Euro (€)	<p>Electricity price during peak hours: cost of electricity drawn from the grid during peak demand hours.</p> <p>Electricity price during off-peak hours: cost of electricity drawn from the grid during off-peak hours, when the batteries are being charged (energy from on-site renewable sources is excluded, as it is not taken from the grid).</p> <p>Number of peak hours: total number of hours during the peak period when energy is supplied by the batteries.</p> <p>Energy discharged during peak hours: total amount of energy discharged from the batteries during peak demand hours.</p>	Hour, Day, Month, Year	Peak demand reduction - cost saving: $\sum (\text{electricity price during peak hours} * n \text{ hours peak} - \text{electricity price during off-peak hours} * \text{number of hours}) * \text{energy discharged during peak hours}$	Building peak demand	The KPI can be assessed daily and then consolidated over longer periods, such as monthly or annually, to gain a comprehensive understanding of the overall energy savings. To correctly assess the indicator, it is essential to have access to reliable data on the building's electricity consumption (real time and historical), energy storage system and energy demand curves (daily) and Electric market curves and forecasts (daily).	0
KPI 37	Energy Storage Capacity	Energy Storage System	Operation	Pilot Site	This KPI measures the maximum amount of energy that can be stored by batteries or other storage systems (e.g. V2G). This indicator is useful for monitoring investments in grid flexibility and decarbonisation, and a year-on-year comparison allows the expansion of the pilot's storage capacity to be assessed.	kWh	Installed Energy Storage Capacity (kWh)	Year	Energy Storage Capacity = $\sum \text{Installed Energy Storage Capacity (kWh)}$	Energy storage capacity installed before WILSON	The KPI can be assessed thanks to the data provided by the pilot and building owners. Only storage capacity (nominal) is required. No sensors required.	1
KPI 38	Number of Electric Vehicle Charging Infrastructure	EV infrastructure	Operation	Pilot Site	The KPI measures the annual number of electric vehicles charging infrastructure (charging points) added to the electricity grid in the pilot boundary. This number can then be compared to the number of the same infrastructure in the pre-WILSON boundary to track the expansion of electric mobility in the pilot over time.	Dimensionless (-)	Number of EV charging infrastructure (charging points) installed and connected to the grid (electricity network) each year.	Year	Number of Electric Vehicle Charging Infrastructure = $\sum \text{Number of Electric Vehicle Charging Infrastructure installed and connected to the grid (electricity network) each year}$	Number of EV charging infrastructure (charging points) installed and connected to the grid (electricity network) before WILSON.	The KPI can be assessed thanks to the data provided by the pilot and building owners and technical partners (DSOs, ESCOs). Only the annual number of EV Charging Points is required. No sensors required.	1
KPI 39	Total EE Discharged from EVs CP	EV infrastructure	Operation	Pilot Site	The KPI measures the total amount of electricity discharged from all EV charging points within a specific period.	kWh/yr	EE discharged: Total amount of electrical energy discharged by EVs charging points (kWh); Time: The reference period used for calculations.	Month, Year	Total EE Discharged from EVs CP = $\text{EE discharged} / \text{time}$	None	The KPI helps to identify and track energy flows within the district. The annual value is also representative of the increase in electric vehicles in the district and the capacity of the charging infrastructure.	1
KPI 40	V2G - Total energy returned to the grid	EV infrastructure	Operation	Pilot Site	The KPI measures the total amount of electric energy returned to the grid from electric vehicles over a specific period.	kWh/yr	EE returned to the Grid: Total amount of electrical energy returned to the grid from V2G Technology (kWh); Time: The reference period used for calculations.	Month, Year	Total EE returned to the GRID = $\text{EE returned} / \text{time}$	None	The KPI helps to identify and track energy flows within the district. The annual value is also representative of the increase of electric vehicles with V2G technology in the district (if applicable).	1
KPI 41	Increased grid optimization from ancillary services	Microgrid Optimization	Operation	Pilot Site	This KPI measures the impact of microgrid optimization solutions, specifically through ancillary services. It evaluates how the system improves stability, flexibility, and energy efficiency by providing services such as load	Ratio (%)	Flexibility response capacity (%) : Ratio of energy adjusted in response to grid signal over total available energy Energy adjusted in response to signals(KWh): Energy dynamically managed to	Day, Month, Year	Flexibility Provided -> Response capacity (%) = $\text{Energy adjusted in response to signals} / \text{Total available energy}$	None	The KPI can be assessed at different time scales (daily, monthly, yearly) to evaluate trends in grid optimization. Reliable data on ancillary services and real-time energy adjustments are required. It is essential to have access to historical data for comparison and	1

Code	KPI Preview	Main Topic	Building Phase	Level of Application	KPI Description	U.m.	Data Requested	Monitoring Frequency	Calculation Method	Baseline and benchmark	Notes and Requirements	Priority
					balancing, demand response, and frequency and voltage support to the main power system.		stabilize or balance the grid Total energy available (kWh): Total energy that can be used for grid optimization				trend analysis. Grid signals and flexibility response should be logged systematically for evaluation.	
KPI 42	Optimal pricing strategies	Microgrid Optimization	Operation	Pilot Site	The purpose of the KPI is to measure how the system optimizes energy costs by integrating market data, demand forecasts and distributed generation (including storage and V2G), ensuring maximum economic efficiency for end users and energy communities.	Ratio (%)	Cost of base scenario (€): Total energy cost without applying optimization strategies, considering standard market prices and consumption patterns. Cost with optimization (€): Total energy cost after implementing optimization strategies, including market integration, demand forecasting, and distributed generation	Month, Year	Energy Cost Reduction - > Cost savings = (Cost of base scenario - Cost with optimization) / Cost of base scenario	None	The KPI is evaluated using market data, energy consumption records and distributed generation metrics. It is essential to compare costs before and after optimisation to assess efficiency. Reliable data on demand forecasts and dynamic pricing models are required	1
KPI 43	System Average Interruption Duration Index Reduction (SAIDI) (Yan-Fu LI, 2021)	Network Asset Management	Operation	Pilot Site	The KPI measures the total time of customers' interruption divided by the total number of customers served. This value must be reduced by 40% (Min) within WILSON.	Hour/Customer	CMI: total time of customers' interruption (hours); NT: number of customers served (Customer);	Year	SAIDI: CMI/NT	SAIDI historical value (pre WILSON).	The value must be reduced by 40% according to WILSON goals. The data required for the assessment of the indicator must be provided by technical partners (DSOs, ESCOs, etc..) and Pilot Owners or Stakeholders.	1
KPI 44	System Average Interruption Frequency Index (SAIFI) (Yan-Fu LI, 2021)	Network Asset Management	Operation	Pilot Site	The KPI measures the total number of service interruptions divided by the total number of customers. This value must be less than 5, according to WILSON.	Interruption/Customer	CI: total number of customers interrupted (interruption); NT: number of customers served (Customer);	Year	SAIFI: CI/NT < 5	SAIFI historical value (pre WILSON).	The value must be lower than 5 according to WILSON Goals. The data required for the assessment of the indicator must be provided by technical partners (DSOs, ESCOs, etc..) and Pilot Owners or Stakeholders.	1
KPI 45	Customer Average Interruption Frequency Index (CAIFI) (Yan-Fu LI, 2021)	Network Asset Management	Operation	Pilot Site	The KPI measures the total number of interruptions divided by the number of customers affected.	interruption/customer affected	CI: total number of customers interrupted (interruption); CN: total number of districts customer who have experienced an interruption during the reporting period (customer affected)	Year	CAIFI: CI/CN	CAIFI historical value (pre WILSON).	The data required for the assessment of the indicator must be provided by technical partners (DSOs, ESCOs, etc..) and Pilot Owners or Stakeholders.	0
KPI 46	Customer Average Interruption Duration Index (CAIDI) (Yan-Fu LI, 2021)	Network Asset Management	Operation	Pilot Site	The KPI measures the monthly/annual hours of network interruption divided by the total number of interruptions.	Hour/Interruption	SAIDI; SAIFI;	Year	CAIDI: SAIDI/SAIFI	CAIDI historical value (pre WILSON).	The data required for the assessment of the indicator must be provided by technical partners (DSOs, ESCOs, etc..) and Pilot Owners or Stakeholders.	0
KPI 47	Customer Total Average Interruption Duration Index (CTAIDI) (Yan-Fu LI, 2021)	Network Asset Management	Operation	Pilot Site	The KPI measures the total time of customers' interruption divided by the number of customers affected.	Hour/Customer affected	CMI: total time of customers' interruption (hours); CN: total number of districts customer who have experienced an interruption during the reporting period (customer affected)	Year	CTAIDI: CMI/CN	CTAIDI historical value (pre WILSON).	The data required for the assessment of the indicator must be provided by technical partners (DSOs, ESCOs, etc..) and Pilot Owners or Stakeholders.	0

Code	KPI Preview	Main Topic	Building Phase	Level of Application	KPI Description	U.m.	Data Requested	Monitoring Frequency	Calculation Method	Baseline and benchmark	Notes and Requirements	Priority
KPI 48	Grid Congestion Hours	Network Asset Management	Operation	Pilot Site	The KPI measures the number of congestion hours, which is the total number of hours in a year when an interconnection is saturated with respect to its available capacity. An interconnection is considered saturated when it reaches 99.99% of its available capacity. This value must be reduced by 15% within WILSON.	hours/year	Congestion hours: number of saturated hours in a year; Annual hours	Year	None	Grid congestion hours historical value (pre WILSON).	The value must be reduced by 15% according to WILSON Proposal. The data required for the assessment of the indicator must be provided by the technical partners involved in grid monitoring and management.	1
KPI 49	Grid-Connected Renewable Installations	Network Asset Management	Operation	Pilot Site	The KPI measures the number of renewable energy systems connected to the grid during and after WILSON.	Dimensionless (-)	Number of RES installations connected to the grid (Electric Network) year by year.	Year	Grid-Connected Renewable Installations = \sum Number of RES installations connected to the grid (Electric Network) year by year.	Number of RES installations connected to the grid before WILSON.	None	1
KPI 50	Maintenance Cost per Asset	Predictive Maintenance	Maintenance	Critical Assets	The KPI assesses the total maintenance costs incurred per asset.	€	Total Maintenance Costs is the sum of all maintenance-related expenses incurred for the assets over a specified period. Number of Assets is the total number of individual assets for which the maintenance costs are being calculated.	Month, Year	Maintenance Cost per Asset = Total Maintenance Costs / Number of Assets	None	The KPI can be applied to any of the critical assets identified at the pilot site. Critical assets in the HVAC systems, including boilers, pumps, radiators and heating coils, fans and filters in the air handling units. To calculate the KPI, it is essential to install sensors for continuous monitoring of the functional parameters of the critical assets (functional parameters: energy consumption, operating hours, functional setpoints).	2
KPI 51	Avoided Maintenance Tasks (MAV)	Predictive Maintenance	Maintenance	Critical Assets	The KPI measure the percentage of scheduled preventive maintenance tasks avoided due to predictive maintenance.	Ratio (%)	Avoided Maintenance Tasks = count of avoided tasks. Total Scheduled Tasks = count of all planned tasks.	Month, Year	MAR = Avoided or Cancelled maintenance task/Total number of maintenance tasks scheduled * 100%	None		2
KPI 52	RUL Lead_time	Predictive Maintenance	Maintenance	Critical Assets	The KPI measures the time between predicted RUL threshold crossing and actual failure/intervention.	hours (h)	Requires tracking of predicted RUL threshold crossing time and actual intervention time.	Month, Year	Lead Time=Time of intervention-Time of RUL threshold crossing	None		2
KPI 53	Incident Rate	Predictive Maintenance	Maintenance	Critical Assets	The KPI assesses the number of safety incidents related to asset failure or maintenance activities.	Dimensionless (-)	Number of Incidents: The total count of safety incidents related to maintenance activities. Total Maintenance Activities: The total number of maintenance activities performed during the period.	Month, Year	Incident Rate = Number of Incidents / Total Maintenance Activities	None		0
KPI 54	Asset Availability	Predictive Maintenance	Maintenance	Critical Assets	The KPI assesses the proportion of time that an asset is available for use.	Ratio (%)	Total Time is the total time the asset was intended to be operational (often referred to as the total time available for operation). Downtime is the time the asset was not operational due to failures, maintenance, or other issues.	Month, Year	Asset availability = (Total Time - Downtime) / Total Time x 100	None		0
KPI 55	Cost Avoidance	Predictive Maintenance	Maintenance	Critical Assets	The KPI assesses the cost savings achieved by preventing failures and extending asset life through predictive maintenance.	Euro (€)	Costs Avoided by Preventative Actions: Repair Costs + Downtime Costs + Replacement Costs + Safety and Compliance Costs. Predictive Maintenance Costs: costs associated with the implementation of predictive maintenance practices, including Labor Costs + Technology Costs + Data Analysis Costs.	Month, Year	Cost Avoidance = Costs Avoided by Preventative Actions - Predictive Maintenance Costs	None	0	

Code	KPI Preview	Main Topic	Building Phase	Level of Application	KPI Description	U.m.	Data Requested	Monitoring Frequency	Calculation Method	Baseline and benchmark	Notes and Requirements	Priority
KPI 56	Failure Rate	Predictive Maintenance	Maintenance	Critical Assets	The KPI assesses the frequency of asset failure within a specific period.	failure/h	Number of Failures is the number of breakdown/failures that occurred during the measured time Total Operational Time is the sum of working hours in good operation	Month, Year	Failure Rate = Number of Failures / Total Operational Time	None		0

5.1.4. Environmental Performance Indicators

Table 5.4 **Error! Reference source not found.** below shows the indicators developed in collaboration with the tool developers that can be considered and assessed to evaluate the environmental performances of pilots and buildings. The main topics are climate change, the impact of operation and renovation on biodiversity (both in-situ and ex-situ) and the heat island effect.

Table 5.4: Environmental Performance Indicators

Code	KPI Preview	Main Topic	Building Phase	Level of Application	KPI Description	U.m.	Data Requested	Monitoring Frequency	Calculation Method	Baseline and benchmark	Notes and Requirements	Priority
KPI 57	Carbon Footprint	Climate Change	All	Pilot Site & Building level	The KPI measures the Global Warming Potential (GWP) intensity, considering all stages of a building's life cycle, from design to end of life. The indicator is expressed in tonnes of CO ₂ equivalent per reference unit. The reference unit can be the available floor area of the building, the number of occupants, the number of beds or patients, depending on the purpose of the building.	TonCO2e/ref.un	GWP (tonCO2eq): Global warming potential assessed at building level, [HIBOU output] Reference Unit: Reference factor used to normalise and benchmark the GWP of the building according to the purpose of the building itself.	Year	GWP Intensity = GWP (tonCO2eq) / Ref.un	GWP Intensity (pre WILSON)	The indicator will be calculated using INN6 [HIBOU] and based on data collected during WP9/10. The software will also allow the assessment of GWP at the pilot site level through changing the boundary conditions and software settings. Once the total GWP of the district is known, it will be possible to compare different buildings within the district. It will then be possible to identify the building with the highest carbon emissions and prioritise interventions.	2
KPI 58	BAFh: Harmonized Biotype Area Factor	In-Situ Biodiversity	All	Pilot Site	The BAFh indicator is calculated as the sum of the land use typologies, each weighted by a coefficient reflecting the biodiversity potential of the surface, divided by the total surface area of the site. This coefficient ranges from 0 to 1, where 0 represents an impermeable surface (highly urbanised) and 1 represents a permeable surface (natural green areas). (Francesca Peroni, 2019) The higher the indicator value, the more permeable and sustainable the area in question.	Dimensionless (-)	BAFh (WILSON): Index calculated after the implementation of the design/renovation solutions proposed by the WILSON project (to-be). [HIBOU Output]	Year	BAFh = BAFh (WILSON)	BAFh Index calculated at the pilot site level, before the implementation of the solutions promoted by the WILSON (BAFh pre WILSON)	The indicator will be calculated using INN6 [HIBOU] and based on data collected during WP9/10. No sensors required.	2
KPI 59	Global Warning for Terrestrial Ecosystem (GWTE)	Ex-Situ Biodiversity	All	Pilot Site & Building level	The GWTE indicator assesses the impact of climate change (global warming) on the terrestrial ecosystem. This indicator is calculated as PDF·m ² ·year, which is the potential number of species per unit area that could disappear over a given period.	PDF·m ² ·yr	GWTE (WILSON): Index calculated after the implementation of the design/renovation solutions proposed by the WILSON project (to-be). [HIBOU Output]	Year	GWTE = GWTE (WILSON)	GWTE Index calculated at the pilot site level, before the implementation of the solutions promoted by the WILSON (GWTE pre WILSON)	The indicator will be calculated using INN6 [HIBOU] and based on data collected during WP9/10. No sensors required.	2
KPI 60	Global Warning for Freshwater Ecosystem (GWFE)	Ex-Situ Biodiversity	All	Pilot Site & Building level	The GWFE indicator assesses the impact of Climate Change (global warming) on the Freshwater Ecosystem. This KPI is calculated as PDF·m ² ·year, which signifies the Potentially Disappeared Fraction of species per unit area over a designated period.	PDF·m ² ·yr	GWFE (WILSON): Index calculated after the implementation of the design/renovation solutions proposed by the WILSON project (to-be). [HIBOU Output]	Year	GWFE = GWFE (WILSON)	GWFE Index calculated at the pilot site level, before the implementation of the solutions promoted by the	The indicator will be calculated using INN6 [HIBOU] and based on data collected during WP9/10. No sensors required.	2

Code	KPI Preview	Main Topic	Building Phase	Level of Application	KPI Description	U.m.	Data Requested	Monitoring Frequency	Calculation Method	Baseline and benchmark	Notes and Requirements	Priority
										WILSON (GWFE pre WILSON);		
KPI 61	Terrestrial Acidification (TA)	Ex-Situ Biodiversity	All	Pilot Site & Building level	The KPI evaluates the effects on soil chemical properties resulting from the deposition of nutrients in acidifying forms. This KPI is calculated as PDF·m ² ·year, which signifies the Potentially Disappeared Fraction of species per unit area over a designated period.	PDF·m ² ·yr	TE (WILSON): Index calculated after the implementation of the design/renovation solutions proposed by the WILSON project (to-be). [HIBOU Output]	Year	TE = TE (WILSON)	TE Index calculated at the pilot site level, before the implementation of the solutions promoted by the WILSON (TE pre WILSON);	The indicator will be calculated using INN6 [HIBOU] and based on data collected during WP9/10. No sensors required.	2
KPI 62	Freshwater Eutrophication (FWEP)	Ex-Situ Biodiversity	All	Pilot Site & Building level	The KPI assesses the pollution process that occurs when a lake or watercourse becomes excessively enriched with plant nutrients, leading to an overgrowth of algae and aquatic plants. When these plants die and decompose, they consume oxygen in the water, rendering the lake, river, or stream lifeless. This KPI is calculated as PDF·m ² ·year, which signifies the Potentially Disappeared Fraction of species per unit area over a designated period.	PDF·m ² ·yr	FWEP (WILSON): Index calculated after the implementation of the design/renovation solutions proposed by the WILSON project (to-be). [HIBOU Output]	Year	FWEP = FWEP (WILSON)	FWEP Index calculated at the pilot site level, before the implementation of the solutions promoted by the WILSON (FWEP pre WILSON);	The indicator will be calculated using INN6 [HIBOU] and based on data collected during WP9/10. No sensors required.	2
KPI 63	Water consumption for Terrestrial ecosystem (WCTE)	Ex-Situ Biodiversity	All	Pilot Site & Building level	The KPI evaluates metabolism of terrestrial ecosystems and the efficiency of water consumption. This indicator is influenced by climate change and has a direct impact on biodiversity, leading to a decline in species. This KPI is calculated as PDF·m ² ·year, which signifies the Potentially Disappeared Fraction of species per unit area over a designated period.	PDF·m ² ·yr	WCTE (WILSON): Index calculated after the implementation of the design/renovation solutions proposed by the WILSON project (to-be). [HIBOU Output]	Year	WCTE = WCTE (WILSON)	WCTE Index calculated at the pilot site level, before the implementation of the solutions promoted by the WILSON (WCTE pre WILSON);	The indicator will be calculated using INN6 [HIBOU] and based on data collected during WP9/10. No sensors required.	2
KPI 64	Water consumption for aquatic ecosystems (WCAE)	Ex-Situ Biodiversity	All	Pilot Site & Building level	The KPI evaluates metabolism of aquatic ecosystems and the efficiency of water consumption. This indicator is influenced by climate change and has a direct impact on biodiversity, leading to a decline in species. This KPI is calculated as PDF·m ² ·year, which signifies the Potentially Disappeared Fraction of species per unit area over a designated period.	PDF·m ² ·yr	WCAE (WILSON): Index calculated after the implementation of the design/renovation solutions proposed by the WILSON project (to-be), [HIBOU Output]	Year	WCAE = WCAE (WILSON)	WCAE Index calculated at the pilot site level, before the implementation of the solutions promoted by the WILSON (WCAE pre WILSON);	The indicator will be calculated using INN6 [HIBOU] and based on data collected during WP9/10. No sensors required.	2
KPI 65	Urban heat Island Intensity (UHI)	Urban Heat Island	All	Pilot Site	This KPI measures the temperature difference between a district and a referenced location (e.g. meteo station).	°C	Average Air Temperature of the referenced district: the value can be assessed through monitoring system; Average Air Temperature of a rural area.	Year	Difference of the hourly air temperatures.	The meteorological station is considered a baseline.	Installation of a meteorological station to monitor the outside temperature of the district/pilot.	2

5.1.5. Building Diagnostic Indicators

Table 5.5 **Error! Reference source not found.** below shows the indicators developed in collaboration with the tool developers that can be considered and assessed to evaluate the building diagnostics of the pilots. The main themes are resilience and SRI indicators. For the BIM SRI indicators, only the 3-Key functionality (KF-01, KF-02, and KF-03) and the Total SRI Index (TSR) were considered out of the 16 different indicators potentially available. The full and detailed explanation of the BIM-SRI INN, including calculation methodology and requirements, can be found in Deliverable 4.3.

Table 5.5: Building Diagnostic Indicators

Code	KPI Preview	Main Topic	Building Phase	Level of Application	KPI Description	U.m.	Data Requested	Monitoring Frequency	Calculation Method	Baseline and benchmark	Notes and Requirements	Priority
KPI 66	Restoration time (100% capacity)	Resilience	Operation	Building level	The KPI measures the number of days required to fully restore the operational capacity of a building to 100% following an extreme event. A baseline is established at the start of the project and the KPI is reassessed each time a proactive measure is implemented that results in a significant improvement, allowing the positive impact on this indicator to be assessed.	Days (d)	Restoration time (WILSON) [INN8 output]	Year	Restoration time: Restoration time (WILSON)	Restoration Time calculated before the implementation of the solutions promoted by WILSON (Restoration time pre WILSON);	The KPI can be reassessed periodically as actions are taken or changes are made. The data required by the INN to provide the result is the description of the overall system and relevant assets, assessment of possible disruptive events and relevant hazard scenarios.	1
KPI 67	Building Robustness Index	Resilience	Operation	Building level	This KPI measures the expected percentage loss in building capacity following an extreme event. A baseline is established at the project's outset, and the KPI is reassessed after any significant proactive measures are implemented, allowing for the evaluation of their positive impact on the indicator.	Ratio (%)	Building Robustness index (WILSON) [INN8 output]	Year	Building Robustness Index: Building Robustness index (WILSON)	Building Robustness index calculated before the implementation of the solutions promoted by WILSON (Building Robustness index pre WILSON);	The KPI can be reassessed periodically as actions are taken or changes are made. The data required by the INN to provide the result is the description of the overall system and relevant assets, assessment of possible disruptive events and relevant hazard scenarios.	2
KPI 68	Ires: Resilience Index	Resilience	Operation	Building level	This KPI measures the overall level of resilience of an asset by considering several indicators, including exposure to hazards, internal and external resources, and preparedness. The resilience score is calculated as a weighted average of these indicators.	Ratio (%)	Resilience Index (WILSON) [INN8 output]	Year	Resilience Index: Resilience Index (WILSON)	Resilience Index calculated before the implementation of the solutions promoted by WILSON (Resilience Index pre WILSON);	The KPI can be reassessed periodically as actions are taken or changes are made. The data required by the INN to provide the result is the description of the overall system and relevant assets, assessment of possible disruptive events and relevant hazard scenarios.	1
KPI 69	Direct Losses Quantification	Resilience	Operation	Building level	This KPI measures the direct losses resulting from structural damage. These losses are quantified at time zero, before the implementation of the WILSON solution, and recalculated afterward to assess the reduction in direct losses achieved through the WILSON implementation.	kiloEuro (k€)	Direct Loss Quantification (WILSON) [INN8 output]	Year	Direct Loss Quantification: Direct Loss Quantification (WILSON)	Direct Loss Quantification calculated before the implementation of the solutions promoted by WILSON (Direct Loss Quantification pre WILSON);	The KPI can be reassessed periodically as actions are taken or changes are made. The data required by the INN to provide the result is the description of the overall system and relevant assets, assessment of possible disruptive events and relevant hazard scenarios.	1
KPI 70	Indirect Losses Quantification	Resilience	Operation	Building level	This KPI measures the indirect losses resulting from structural damage. These losses are quantified at time zero, before the implementation of the WILSON solution, and recalculated afterwards to assess the reduction in direct losses achieved by the WILSON implementation.	kiloEuro (k€)	Indirect Loss Quantification (WILSON) [INN8 output]	Year	Indirect Loss Quantification: Indirect Loss Quantification (WILSON)	Indirect Loss Quantification calculated before the implementation of the solutions promoted by WILSON (Indirect Loss Quantification pre WILSON);	The KPI can be reassessed periodically as actions are taken or changes are made. The data required by the INN to provide the result is the description of the overall system and relevant assets, assessment of possible disruptive events and relevant hazard scenarios.	1
KPI 71	Level of Service	Resilience	Operation	Building level	This KPI measures the level of service of the asset (building) prior to an event. The indicator can be compared to the district's average to help prioritize interventions. Additionally, it can be evaluated before and after the implementation of WILSON solutions to assess improvements.	Dimensionless (-)	Level of Service (WILSON) [INN8 output]	Year	Level of Service: Level of Service (WILSON)	Level of Service calculated before the implementation of the solutions promoted by the WILSON (Level of Service pre WILSON);	The KPI can be reassessed periodically as actions are taken or changes are made. The data required by the INN to provide the result is the description of the overall system and relevant assets, assessment of possible disruptive events and relevant hazard scenarios.	1

Code	KPI Preview	Main Topic	Building Phase	Level of Application	KPI Description	U.m.	Data Requested	Monitoring Frequency	Calculation Method	Baseline and benchmark	Notes and Requirements	Priority
KPI 72	Energy savings and operation (KF-01)	Smart Readiness Indicators	Design, Operation, Maintenance and Renovation	Building level	The KPI reports the Energy Saving and Operation SRI indicator calculated by the INN9. The KPI can be assessed during the design and use phase the building (e.g. use, maintenance, renovation) and can facilitate the comparison of the building's score before and after the innovations and measures proposed in the WILSON project.	Ratio (%)	Energy savings and operation score (WILSON) [INN9 output]	Month, Year	Energy savings and operation score = Energy savings and operation score (WILSON)	Energy savings and operation score (pre WILSON)	The KPI can be assessed during the design, operation, maintenance, and renovation phases. However, comparisons can only be made if actions or changes have been made since the initial assessment. All necessary data for the evaluation of the BIM-SRI indicators shall be provided. The calculation method for the evaluation of these indicators shall be developed, tested, and verified.	2
KPI 73	Respond to user needs (KF-02)	Smart Readiness Indicators	Design, Operation, Maintenance and Renovation	Building level	The KPI reports the Responsiveness to User Needs SRI indicator. The KPI can be assessed during the design and use phase of the building (e.g. use, maintenance, renovation) and can facilitate the comparison of the building's score before and after the innovations and measures proposed in the WILSON project.	Ratio (%)	Respond to user needs score (WILSON) [INN9 output]	Month, Year	Respond to user needs score = Respond to user needs score (WILSON)	Respond to user needs score (pre WILSON)	The KPI can be assessed during the design, operation, maintenance, and renovation phases. However, comparisons can only be made if actions or changes have been made since the initial assessment. All necessary data for the evaluation of the BIM-SRI indicators shall be provided. The calculation method for the evaluation of these indicators shall be developed, tested, and verified.	2
KPI 74	Energy Flexibility Score (KF-03)	Smart Readiness Indicators	Design, Operation, Maintenance and Renovation	Building level	The KPI reports the Energy Flexibility SRI indicator. The KPI can be assessed during the design and use phase the building (e.g. use and renovation) and can facilitate the comparison of the building's score before and after the innovations and measures proposed in the WILSON project.	Ratio (%)	Energy Flexibility score (WILSON) [INN9 output]	Month, Year	Energy Flexibility Score improvement = Energy Flexibility score (WILSON)	Energy Flexibility score (pre WILSON)	The KPI can be assessed during the design, operation, maintenance, and renovation phases. However, comparisons can only be made if actions or changes have been made since the initial assessment. All necessary data for the evaluation of the BIM-SRI indicators shall be provided. The calculation method for the evaluation of these indicators shall be developed, tested, and verified.	2
KPI 75	Total SRI Score (TSR)	Smart Readiness Indicators	Design, Operation, Maintenance and Renovation	Building level	The KPI reports the building's overall SRI score. The KPI can be assessed during the design and use phase the building (e.g. use and renovation) and can facilitate the comparison of the building's score before and after the innovations and measures proposed in the WILSON project.	Ratio (%)	Total SRI score (WILSON) [INN9 output]	Month, Year	Total SRI score improvement = Total SRI score (WILSON)	Total SRI score (pre WILSON)	The KPI can be assessed during the design, operation, maintenance, and renovation phases. However, comparisons can only be made if actions or changes have been made since the initial assessment. All necessary data for the evaluation of the BIM-SRI indicators shall be provided. The calculation method for the evaluation of these indicators shall be developed, tested, and verified.	2

5.1.6. Techno-economic Indicators

Table 5.6 **Error! Reference source not found.** below shows the indicators developed in collaboration with the tool developers that can be considered and assessed to evaluate the techno-economic benefits of renovations. The KPIs can be used by any pilot interested in assessing the performance improvements, renovation benefits or resilience upgrades achieved through specific investments (or with existing budget).

Table 5.6: Techno-economic Indicators

Code	KPI Preview	Main Topic	Building Phase	Level of Application	KPI Description	U.m.	Data Requested	Monitoring Frequency	Calculation Method	Baseline and benchmark	Notes and Requirements	Priority
KPI 76	Payback Time (PBT)	Technoeconomic Investment	Operation & Renovation	Building level	The payback period of an investment (or existing budget if the investment cannot be made) is the time it takes for positive cash flows to compensate for the outlay. This indicator can also be used to compare different project solutions at an early stage and help stakeholders to identify the most technically and economically advantageous solution.	year	Availability of techno-economic data on the proposed investment (or existing Budget): Initial investment; Annual payback;	Year	Payback Period = Initial Investment / Annual Payback	No needed.	The PBT can be compared between different solutions to see which is the most cost-effective. However, to calculate this indicator, a technical-economic description of the initiative is necessary.	1
KPI 77	Return on investment (ROI)	Technoeconomic Investment	Operation & Renovation	Building level	This KPI measures the ratio of net income (over a period) to investment (or existing budget if the investment cannot be made). This indicator can also be used to compare different project solutions at an early stage, helping stakeholders to identify the most technically and economically advantageous solution.	Ratio (%)	Availability of techno-economic data on the proposed investment (or existing Budget): Net returns; Cost of investment;	Year	ROI = (Net Return on Investment/Cost of Initial Investment) ×100	No needed.	The ROI can be compared between different solutions to see which is the most cost-effective. However, to calculate this indicator, a technical-economic description of the initiative is necessary.	1
KPI 78	Property value increase	Technoeconomic Investment	Operation & Renovation	Building level	This KPI measures the estimated increase in value of the property because of upgrades/renovations. This KPI can be used to assist stakeholders in making the most cost effective decision, but more generally to quantify the increase in value of the property once the upgrades/renovations have been completed.	Ratio (%)	Pre-renovation property value; Post-renovation property value;	Year	Property Value Increase: ((Post-renovation property value – Pre-renovation property value) / Pre-renovation property value) x 100	Pre-renovation property value;	None	1
KPI 79	Energy savings per investment amount	Technoeconomic Investment	Operation & Renovation	Building level	The KPI measures the relationship between the energy savings achieved through renovation or innovation activities and the investment made (or existing budget if the investment cannot be made). This indicator can also be used to compare different project solutions at an early stage and help stakeholders to identify the most technically and economically advantageous solution.	TEP/(euro*year)	Availability of techno-economic data on the proposed investment (or existing Budget): Energy Saving achieved through renovation or innovation activities; Investment amount;	Year	Energy savings per investment amount: Energy Saving / Investment amount	None	The indicator can be used to compare different solutions to see which is the most cost-effective. However, to calculate this indicator, a technical-economic description of the initiative is required. In addition, energy baseline/consumption is required.	1
KPI 80	Carbon savings per investment amount	Technoeconomic Investment	Operation & Renovation	Building level	The KPI measures the relationship between the carbon savings achieved through renovation or innovation activities and the investment made (or existing budget if the investment cannot be made). It can also be used to compare different project solutions at an early stage, helping stakeholders to identify the most technically and economically advantageous solution.	TonCO2e/(euro*year)	Availability of techno-economic data on the proposed investment (or existing Budget): Carbon Saving achieved through renovation or innovation activities; Investment amount;	Year	Carbon savings per investment amount: Carbon Saving / Investment amount	None	The indicator can be used to compare different solutions to see which is the most cost-effective. However, to calculate this indicator, a technical-economic description of the initiative is required. In addition, carbon emissions baseline/consumption is required.	1

5.2. Contingency KPIs

Of the total number of indicators proposed above, 6 were also considered as high-priority contingency KPIs, as they can be calculated even if the objectives, innovations, and benefits expected from the project are inadequate or the sensors not properly in place.

In particular, these indicators are of a high level and allow to characterise and evaluate the subject's performance (pilot, building or asset), allowing comparisons with best practices even without the implementation of renovation scenarios or management actions.

The Italian pilot, which is currently in the process of rehabilitation, has confirmed the availability of data (e.g. energy consumption) for the future, allowing these indicators to be calculated.

The indicators are:

- **KPI 3: Data Completeness (mandatory data):** the chosen indicator makes it possible to quantify the availability of mandatory data necessary for the implementation and proper functioning of the innovations proposed by the WILSON project. Even if there are gaps or misalignments in the project, the indicator remains of interest to better understand the level of information available at each pilot site and to promote data collection and monitoring activities;
- **KPI 19: Asset Use Intensity:** the indicator allows asset performance monitoring over time. It also provides intrinsic information about the management and optimization of energy flows. For a large portion of assets in participating pilots, HVAC and lighting systems are already monitored or planned to be monitored. For this reason, the indicator was selected because the data required for the assessment is easy to find;
- **KPI 29: Energy Consumption (use phase):** the indicator, which can be applied at different scales, provides a simple and comparable indication of energy consumption. If the building does not have energy flow monitoring and allocation systems for individual areas and/or activities (e.g. hospital wards), the indicator can be easily assessed at building level by collecting available energy measures or bills;
- **KPI 30: Energy Intensity (use phase):** based on the previous indicator, energy intensity can be easily assessed by dividing the energy consumption by the reference unit of interest. The indicator allows comparison over time of the same building or benchmark activity in order to identify improvements;
- **KPI 32: Carbon Emissions (use phase):** considering the energy consumption related to the use phase above, the related carbon emissions can be evaluated by multiplying the standardised and/or national emission factors for the consumption of the different energy vectors;
- **KPI 33: Carbon Intensity (use phase):** the indicator can be easily derived from the carbon emissions above, by dividing the use phase emissions by the reference unit of interest. The indicator allows comparison over time of the same building or benchmark activity in order to identify potential improvements.

Additional contingency KPIs may be identified from the remaining list of lower priority indicators according to the future development of the project and pilots.

6. HIGH-PRIORITY KPIs FOR BASELINE ASSESSMENT AND MONITORING PLAN

As a result of internal discussions in WP4, it was decided to identify which of the higher priority indicators may support the definition of a performance baseline for the four different pilots, according to their actual status and interest. This selection also allowed the definition of a first draft monitoring plan.

These baseline KPIs can vary from pilot to pilot, e.g. the Italian pilot managed by Agenzia del Demanio is in the process of rehabilitation and the indicator related to the building use phase cannot really be assessed for a baseline definition. The remaining three pilots, which have operational buildings, can be assessed for both the use phase and the whole life cycle.

Another important aspect is that buildings within the same pilot can differ in terms of available and accessible data. The aim of the following sections is to identify the main KPIs that could be assessed in general for each pilot, without going into the details of each individual building. This level of details will be reached during the upcoming development and monitoring phase.

In conclusion, in addition to these high priority KPIs, it is recommended not to stop the analysis of these indicators, but to include in the later stages of development and monitoring all the lower priority indicators mentioned in the “Panel of KPI” relevant to each demonstrator.

6.1. Italian Demosite: Ex-Caserma Papa

The Italian pilot, known as “Ex-Caserma Papa”, is undergoing a deeper renovation led by the Agenzia del Demanio (ADD). The project will integrate new and renovated buildings, with the ultimate aim of improving efficiency in resource management, energy consumption, comfort, and material use. The main objective is to transform the area into a central hub for Public Administration offices, integrating renewable energy sources to limit the environmental impact and digital BIM solutions to optimise operational strategies.

As there are no functional and operational buildings within the boundary of the pilot at the time of writing (M10), it has not been possible to identify potential baseline indicators related to the use phase of the buildings. However, once the buildings are constructed and in operation, energy performance during the use phase may also be assessed and additional indicators included into the dedicated monitoring plan.

For this reason and, considering the involvement of the pilot in use cases focused on biodiversity, resilience and renovation, the KPIs usable for characterising the actual status of the pilot are mainly related to carbon footprint, biodiversity (both in- and ex-situ), climate change (urban heat island) and resilience, as reported in the following table. In addition, as the BIM SRI indicators can be assessed in relation to the design phase, they have been included in the list below.

Once the buildings are constructed and in operation, the energy performance during the use phase may also be assessed and compared with the design performance.

Table 6.1: High-Priority/Baseline KPIs for Italian Pilot

Code	KPI Preview
KPI 3	Data Completeness (mandatory data)
KPI 5	Data quality
KPI 57	Carbon Footprint
KPI 58	BAFh: Harmonized Biotype Area Factor
KPI 59	Global Warning for Terrestrial Ecosystem (GWTE)
KPI 60	Global Warning for Freshwater Ecosystem (GWFE)
KPI 61	Terrestrial Acidification (TA)
KPI 62	Freshwater Eutrophication (FWEP)
KPI 63	Water consumption for Terrestrial ecosystem (WCTE)
KPI 64	Water consumption for aquatic ecosystems (WCAE)
KPI 65	Urban heat Island Intensity (UHI)
KPI 67	Building Robustness Index
KPI 72	Energy savings and operation
KPI 73	Respond to user needs
KPI 74	Energy Flexibility Score
KPI 75	Total SRI Score

6.2. Spanish Demosite: Hospital del Mar

The Spanish pilot, called Hospital del Mar, is a hospital and, as is well known from the scientific literature, hospitals are responsible for about 5% of the world's total energy consumption due to their continuous operation.

The pilot site consists of two different buildings:

- Building B, completed in 2017, houses the key hospital areas, administrative offices, and a data centre;
- Building C, which was completed in June 2024, houses several patient beds, operating theatres, and an intensive care unit.

For this reason, and also in line with the hospital's interest and use cases, the KPIs that could be used to characterise the current state of the buildings within the pilot are mainly related to energy consumption and efficiency, such as asset intensity, including lighting and HVAC systems, energy consumption and intensity during the use phase, as well as carbon emissions and carbon intensity, carbon footprint and BIM-SRI indicators.

The Spanish pilot will be the forerunner of two different use cases, one related to energy monitoring and optimisation and the other related to techno-economic investment planning for property owners. To evaluate the results achieved through the implementation of the use cases, it is recommended to select from the attached "Panel of KPIs" the additional indicators that best meet the objective of each use case.

Predictive maintenance, although a critical issue for the hospitals, was not selected because it was considered of medium priority by the pilot itself. In addition, the pilot is not a forerunner in the area of predictive maintenance.

Table 6.2: High-Priority/Baseline KPIs for Spanish Pilot

Code	KPI Preview
KPI 3	Data Completeness (mandatory data)
KPI 5	Data quality
KPI 19	Asset Use Intensity
KPI 20	HVAC Use Intensity (Winter Season)
KPI 20	HVAC Use Intensity (Cooling Season)
KPI 29	Energy Consumption (Usage Phase)
KPI 30	Energy Intensity (Usage Phase)
KPI 32	Carbon Emissions (Use Phase)
KPI 33	Carbon Intensity (Use Phase)
KPI 72	Energy savings and operation
KPI 73	Respond to user needs
KPI 74	Energy Flexibility Score
KPI 75	Total SRI Score

6.3. UK Demosite: Newcastle HELIX

The UK Pilot, located in Newcastle HELIX, a pioneering district and dynamic hub for research, business, and residential development, is the third large pilot of the WILSON Project.

The UK Demosite comprises three main buildings, each representing a different sector and function. The key features of each of them are summarised below:

- The Core, a large commercial building that provides workspace for SMEs, as well as office and meeting rooms, and is home to technology companies;
- The Spark: A modern office and collaboration space that supports a growing network of businesses and innovators; and
- The Urban Sciences Building (USB), a higher education structure that can be described as a true living laboratory for the study of urban sustainability and smart city innovation.

The UK pilot will include other buildings, but at this stage, the work is focused on these three specific buildings.

Due to its operational status, it may be possible to identify different indicators to assess the actual performance of the buildings, especially in terms of energy consumption.

Furthermore, as the Pilot is the frontrunner of Use Case 4, related to predictive maintenance, the high-priority KPIs related to maintenance have been included in the list below.

It is also the leader of Use Case 1, which relates to decentralised multi-source data management. Several indicators about Innovation 1, 2 and 3 were proposed in the "Panel of

KPIs” but, as they are not strictly related to building performance, they have not been included in the list below.

In fact, Table 6.3 represents the only high-priority indicators that, considering the current stage of the pilot, could be used to assess the pilot baseline and the future evaluation of the positive impact of the WILSON project.

Further performance indicators, in addition to those listed below, may be considered in the subsequent development and monitoring phases according to the characteristics of the Demosite.

Table 6.3: High-Priority/Baseline KPIs for UK Pilot

Code	KPI Title
KPI 3	Data Completeness (mandatory data)
KPI 5	Data quality
KPI 19	Asset Use Intensity
KPI 20	HVAC Use Intensity (Winter Season)
KPI 20	HVAC Use Intensity (Cooling Season)
KPI 29	Energy Consumption (Usage Phase)
KPI 30	Energy Intensity (Usage Phase)
KPI 32	Carbon Emissions (Use Phase)
KPI 33	Carbon Intensity (Use Phase)
KPI 50	Maintenance Cost per Asset
KPI 51	Avoided Maintenance Tasks (MAV)
KPI 52	RUL Lead time
KPI 72	Energy savings and operation
KPI 73	Respond to user needs
KPI 74	Energy Flexibility Score
KPI 75	Total SRI Score

6.4. Swiss Demosite: Building Park Uzwil

The last pilot involved in the WILSON Project is the Swiss one. It is located in the northeast of Switzerland and cover the SAK service area, which includes St. Gallen, Appenzell-Innerrhoden, and Appenzell-Ausserrhoden.

The core demosite is the Building Park Uzwil, owned by SAK, which includes 21 apartments, serving as the primary testing ground for the pilot. Additionally, manufacturers such as WATTX engage further buildings in the pilot. In total, the Swiss large-scale pilot will involve 200 buildings, comprising 80% residential, 5% commercial, and 15% public buildings, with a mix of modern and older constructions.

Given the large and diverse nature of the pilot, the table below shows the Indicators that could be used to assess the performances of Pilot buildings. For the existing building, the

energy-related indicators could be assessed, and a baseline performance could be established.

The Swiss Pilot is then the frontrunner of the remaining two Use Cases (3 and 8), which are related to the network asset management and green energy investments. The key target groups of the two different UCs are DSOs, ESCOs, operators and public entities, and various indicators have been proposed in the Panel of KPI to assess the objectives of each use case. However, these indicators have not been included in the list below, as they are not related to building assessment, but to network management and grid decarbonisation.

Further performance indicators, in addition to those listed in the attached table, may be considered in the subsequent development and monitoring phases based on the characteristics of the demosite.

Table 6.4: High-Priority/Baseline KPIs for Swiss Pilot

Code	KPI Preview
KPI 3	Data Completeness (mandatory data)
KPI 5	Data quality
KPI 19	Asset Use Intensity
KPI 20	HVAC Use Intensity (Winter Season)
KPI 20	HVAC Use Intensity (Cooling Season)
KPI 29	Energy Consumption (Usage Phase)
KPI 30	Energy Intensity (Usage Phase)
KPI 32	Carbon Emissions (Use Phase)
KPI 33	Carbon Intensity (Use Phase)
KPI 72	Energy savings and operation
KPI 73	Respond to user needs
KPI 74	Energy Flexibility Score
KPI 75	Total SRI Score

7. CONCLUSIONS

The work started with a detailed analysis of the "Suit of Solutions" proposed by the WILSON environment. The study focused on understanding the scope of each solution (INN) and how it interacts with the different phases of the building lifecycle to deliver positive benefits.

Secondly, using a multi-stage methodology and the S.M.A.R.T. framework, the Panel of KPIs was technically developed to cover all the macro issues proposed by the project itself and to support the identification of key sensors for the further monitoring and development plan.

The work has been conducted with the support and effort of project partners, each contributing their specific expertise. In summary, a total of 80 KPIs have been developed. Among these:

- 5 KPIs are general and applicable to all innovation clusters as they relate to data quality and completeness.
- 12 KPIs were identified for Cluster 1, entitled "Data and Interoperability Toolset".
- 39 KPIs were identified for Cluster 2, entitled "Planning and Management Toolset".
- 9 KPIs were identified for Cluster 3, entitled "Environmental Performance Toolset".
- 10 KPIs were identified for Cluster 4, entitled "Building Diagnostics Toolset".
- 5 KPIs were identified for the Investment Planning Tool.

Of these, 30 KPIs were given the highest priority, while 6 were considered as high-priority contingency KPIs. Additional contingency KPIs may be identified from the remaining list of lower priority indicators.

The proposed KPIs cover a wide range of macro issues and will be used for the further monitoring and demonstration strategy, including:

- Energy Efficiency and Renewable Energy;
- Energy Performance, SRI, and Energy Storage;
- Predictive Maintenance;
- Climate Change, Biodiversity and Urban Heat Island;
- Comfort and Ventilation System;
- Data and Service Marketplace;
- Data Quality, Storage & Completeness;
- EV Infrastructure and Microgrid Optimization;
- PDHs, Scalability and Replicability;
- Techno-economic Investment.

The set of KPIs was defined on the basis of a robust survey campaign and specific assumptions were discussed in detail in regular meetings.

The high-priority KPIs were linked to the different pilots in order to identify a first set of high-level indicators that could potentially be used for a baseline definition and initial monitoring plan, while the remaining indicators of lower priority are reported to encourage discussion among the project partners and to identify the specificities of pilots and use cases that could be monitored in the upcoming implementation and evaluation phase.

In conclusion, the monitoring and evaluation of the proposed KPIs will allow to measure not only the level of innovation of the tools provided, but also the performance of the buildings and the whole portfolio. This monitoring will cover not only energy aspects, but also comfort, vulnerability, biodiversity, financial and data management. In addition, these indicators can be used to assess the benefits of possible future renovation measures, providing decision support for stakeholders with a particular focus on the entire life cycle.

Given the significant number of indicators proposed, including those that have been prioritised, it is recommended that their applicability is reviewed during the project development.

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